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Deliverable D2.2: Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of Task 2.2 “Case studies on the use of new media in crisis situations” was for COSMIC to examine a series of European and international case studies of different types of crises in order to explore the ways in which new communication technologies and applications are being used in crisis situations today. Partners conducted an examination of eight different case studies, during which partners described the nature of the case study, provided an understanding of how new and more conventional technologies were used and discussed the lessons learned from the use (or lack of) of those technologies. Specific case studies examined in this report can be seen in the table below.

Table 1: Case studies included in this report

2013 Boston Marathon Bombing
2013 U.K. Heatwave
2012 Sandy Superstorm
2010 Haiti Earthquake
2013 Gezi Protests
2012 Colorado Wildfires
2012 U.K. Floods
2010 Xynthia Storm

Findings from the examination of case studies suggest that in the majority of situations, with the exception of the Xynthia storm which hit France in 2010, social media were used quite extensively. Partners presented how new communication technologies and social media were used based on the following six functions of social media in crisis situations established in COSMIC D2.1 *Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their*

applications:

1. One-way communication (notify/alert)
2. Two-way communication (converse/provide feedback)
3. Request/offer assistance
4. Relay (share a piece of information with others)
5. Campaign (awareness raising/fund raising)
6. Organise (co-ordinate response/enable individuals to organise themselves)¹

Even though in the majority of the examined cases social media were used extensively offering a variety of functions and while they substantially helped the public to deal with the effects of a crisis, some cases such as for instance the U.K. heatwave of 2013, indicate that it may still be early time to solely rely on social media as a crisis management tool when dealing with a crisis.

Also, in most of the case studies, apart from the case study of Sandy where the U.S. Department of Homeland Security documented “Technology, Process, and Policy Gaps Requiring Further Discussion” in order for social media to be used as a crisis management tool and mission-critical grade telecommunications systems, partners identified a shortage of effort on the authorities’ part to draw conclusions on the use of social media and try to incorporate them in their own formal standard response mechanisms.

¹ Watson, et al., op. cit., 2013.

Key points from the examination of European and international case studies include:

- Some case studies demonstrated that there is a high risk of misuse of social media. Kinds of misuse include the following:
 - spreading of rumours and falsehoods,
 - bogus donation requests for individuals posing as official response and support channels,
 - tweeting by the public for help when they should be using conventional channels,
 - sharing confidential police information, such as the location of officers in the case of the Boston bombings and,
 - potential misuse by mainstream media for the sake of speed instead of accuracy and correctness in their news flow.
- When tweeting, hashtags should be well defined to avoid irrelevant content from being displayed on online discussions concerning the event.
- Even though social media are used during an event, does not always mean that a wider audience will be reached.
- Journalists may henceforth take on an active role assisting and participating in the efforts of first responders.
- In many respects, the use of social media may be driven by a lack of alternatives from mainstream media.
- Social media can act as counterbalance when conventional warning systems fail to operate.
- Several cases indicate that it would be wise for organizations and authorities to utilize both traditional media technologies and social media when supporting and communicating with the public

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of new media applications, including for instance, social networking sites such as Facebook and Twitter, have given a new lease of life to the abilities of those involved in crisis response to not only communicate with one another, but crucially has enhanced their abilities to communicate with members of the public affected by a crisis. Not restricted to the response phase of a crisis, new media applications are also able to contribute to preparedness and recover phases on a crisis. The focus of the present report is for COSMIC to explore the ways in which new communication technologies and applications have been used in recent crisis situations. By doing so it will fulfil its objective of preparing 8 to 10 short case studies to examine the recent use of new media in crisis situations.

Accordingly, drawing on the taxonomy of crisis situations described in Tasks 1.1 and 1.2; man-made crises, extreme temperatures, floods, wildfire, storms and earthquakes, partners have selected eight case studies of crisis situations where there has been a “known” use of new media applications to help aid crisis response. These case studies consist of both European and international examples to help partners compare new and relatively more conventional technologies in terms of their relative effectiveness in coordination of response efforts, dissemination of information to the public, and mobilisation of assistance and volunteers. In addition, building on work from Deliverable 2.1, “Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications”², by examining these case studies partners will be able to further study, in detail, innovative uses of new media for purposes other than those originally envisaged (e.g., use of location based social media to disseminate information from the location of an emergency).

Within the current chapter, partners will provide further information relating to the evolution of new media, particularly within its known use within crisis response. Partners will also examine the use of new media in everyday life in order to demonstrate the infiltration of new media in society. The chapter will conclude by providing the reader with further information as to how the report will proceed, including an identification of the case studies being examined.

1.1 USE OF NEW MEDIA IN EVERYDAY LIFE

Understanding Europeans use of the Internet in everyday life, as well as the ways in which Europeans choose to communicate (i.e., what devices they commonly use) will go some way to providing the COSMIC consortium an understanding of how Europeans may send or receive information. Such findings will serve to further complement the consortiums understanding of the potential that engagement with new media could have to help aid crisis response in Europe.

² Watson, H., Finn, R., Wadhwa, K and Yannopoulos, A., “Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications”, *Deliverable 2.1 of the COSMIC project*, September 2013. [p. 52]

A Special Eurobarometer (a public opinion survey) on Cyber, published in July 2012 provides some information regarding European's use of the Internet.³ The survey was carried out on behalf of the European Commission by TNS Opinion and Social. Field work took place between the 10th and 25th March 2012 in 27 EU Member States, to 26,593 respondents from different social and demographic backgrounds.

The survey suggests that use of the Internet in European Member States is widespread⁴, only 29% of respondents claimed they had never accessed the Internet. For those that did access the web, they did so on a frequent basis; 39% accessed the Internet several times a day, 14% claimed they accessed the Internet once a day, 10% stated they used the Internet several times a week, and 6% stated that they used the web no more than once a week.⁵ For those that had never accessed the Internet, they were mostly likely to come from: Portugal (58%), Bulgaria (47%), Romania (47%), Greece (44%) and Cyprus (42%).⁶ Use of the Internet was highest in Denmark, the Netherlands and Sweden.⁷

As seen in the figure⁸ below, findings from the survey suggest several important conclusions with regard to Internet usage and demographic details:⁹

- People aged over 55 are less likely to use the Internet than younger age groups;
- Those that stayed in education until the age of 20+ are also more likely to use the Internet most frequently;
- Internet use was also found to be higher among men than women;
- Internet use was also higher in large towns and cities than in small villages and rural areas.¹⁰

³ TNS Opinion and Social, "Special Eurobarometer 390: Cyber Security", *European Commission*, July 2013. http://ec.europa.eu/public_opinion/archives/ebs/ebs_390_en.pdf

⁴ Information about individual EU Member States access of the Internet can be found in the full report.

⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 7.

⁶ *Ibid.*

⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 10.

⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 9.

¹⁰ Perhaps due to accessibility.

QE1 How often do you access the Internet (e.g., for sending emails, reading online news, chatting with friends or buying products online)?

	At least once a day	At least once a week	At least once a month	Less often	Never	DK
EU27	53%	13%	3%	2%	29%	0%
Sex						
Male	57%	13%	3%	2%	25%	0%
Female	49%	14%	3%	2%	32%	0%
Age						
15-24	84%	10%	1%	1%	4%	0%
25-39	72%	15%	1%	2%	10%	0%
40-54	54%	18%	3%	3%	22%	0%
55+	27%	10%	2%	2%	58%	1%
Education (End of)						
15-	17%	8%	2%	2%	70%	1%
16-19	49%	18%	3%	3%	27%	0%
20+	75%	13%	2%	1%	9%	0%
Still studying	92%	7%	0%	0%	1%	0%

Figure 1: Internet use in European Member States

Within Europe, when accessing the Internet, users are most likely to be at home (80%) or at work (15%), only 1% claimed they used Internet whilst on the move, which is perhaps indicative of the quality of connectivity whilst on the move.¹¹ When asked how they access the Internet, many respondents stated that they used a computer (97%), 26% of respondents stated that they also used a mobile device (e.g., smart phone or tablet).

As a final area of interest for COSMIC is users online activities; 85% stated that they use e-mail, 64% states they read the news online, 53% stated they used the Internet to buy goods and services, 52% used social networking websites, 48% stated they use the web for online banking, 27% use the Internet to play games and 20% use the Internet for business purposes (to sell goods or services).¹² Use of social networking sites was highest in Latvia (69%), Malta (68%), Greece (68%) and Slovakia (66%), use of social networking sites was found to be lowest in Germany (37%).¹³ From a demographic perspective, the usage of social networking sites is higher among younger age groups (79%).¹⁴

- These findings go some way to informing the consortium of Internet usage in Europe. It is evident that Internet use and activities are different across EU Member States which may impact the extent to which new media communications are utilised in European case studies examined in this report. Where applicable, partners will further examine the impact of Internet use in their examination of selected case studies for this report. Crucially the vast number of users accessing the web is indicative of the importance of examining the role that new media tools can have in contributing to crisis management activities, particularly those that involve engagement with the

¹¹ Ibid., p. 11.

¹² Ibid., p. 18.

¹³ Ibid., p. 20.

¹⁴ Ibid., p. 21.

public, for the Internet provides a means of communicating and engaging vast numbers of citizens.

1.2 NEW MEDIA APPLICATIONS & CRISIS MANAGEMENT

Deliverable 2.1 of the COSMIC project, involved partners conducting a baseline analysis of communication technologies and new media applications within crisis management.¹⁵ As part of this work partners referred to the work of Flew who defined new media by the three C's; "computing and information technology, communication networks and digitised media content which stems from convergence; that is the combination of computing, communications and (digital) content".¹⁶ As identified by partners, "new media is of particular interest due to its ability to enable a more "social" form of communication of various digital objects. In particular, some new media applications allow for greater interaction and the ability to edit and share digital data between users".¹⁷

In D2.1, partners sought to investigate the evolution of new media application within crisis management, and were able to demonstrate that many applications provide users with access to visual information, as well as the means to interact with other people, and to share and receive information. Applications assessed within this exercise found that applications ranged from social networking applications such as Facebook, Twitter and YouTube to tailor-made crisis management tools and applications that could be accessed via the web and/or mobile devices. These tools provide various stakeholders with the opportunity to co-ordinate and collaborate to respond to an emerging crises, as well as preparing for future crises.

Crucially, D2.1 highlights the functionality of different applications for the purpose of crisis management. As included in D2.1, the following figure provides further information relating to the different functions that new media applications may perform:

¹⁵ Watson, H., Finn, R., Wadhwa, K and Yannopoulos, A., "Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications", *Deliverable 2.1 of the COSMIC project*, September 2013.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 7.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

Figure 2: New media application by function - D2.1 of the COSMIC project

As can be seen above and discussed further in D2.1, most applications performed the vital role of one-way communication and enabled the sharing of information that enabled individuals to organise themselves. However, some new media applications went a step further by providing additional functionality including the ability to enable users to participate in two-way communication, request and offer assistance, relay information and to help with campaigning activities. Partners were able to conclude that it was evident that applications provide different functionality that may or may not be suitable for responding to a crisis, and that accordingly a “one size fits all” approach does not apply to the use of new media applications in crisis situations. Rather, stakeholders should consider their individual needs in crises and utilise the appropriate applications to meet those needs”.¹⁸ Within the current report, in part, partners will seek to further understand, from the case studies examined what functions were served through the use of new media applications.

The use of new media applications to aid crisis management activities has been well received within the scientific community. In particular, numerous studies have been useful for informing us about the value of social media in crisis situations, but they do not always tell us about the value of new media applications overall. For instance, a study of by Taylor et al. from 2013 revealed results from a survey of members of the public following cyclone Yasi in Australia and New Zealand in 2011 revealed that a substantial number of individuals were turning to social media for updates for up-to-date information relating to the unfolding crisis.¹⁹ The study not only revealed that people were seeking out information via social media, but in addition, people were using social media to share information with others in their network. Elsewhere a study by Novak and Vidoloff (2011) demonstrated how throughout the devastating 2007 California wildfires, citizens were using social media

¹⁸ Ibid., p. 52.

¹⁹ Taylor, M., Wells, G., Howell, G., and Raphael, B, “The Role of Social Media as Psychological First Aid as a Support to Community Resilience Building”. *The Australian Journal of Emergency Management*, Vol. 27, No.1, 2012, pp. 20–26.

applications to pool information to run a citizen journalism based platform for the dissemination of localised information.²⁰

Some studies have also demonstrated the risks involved in using social media in a crisis. For instance, in the wake of Hurricane Sandy in the US in October 2012, a study by Burgess et al. examined the diffusion of fake images on Twitter depicting events.²¹ Despite widespread discussion of fake images within the news media, Burgess et al.’s analysis of 50 images suggested that whilst some accounts were considered “fake”, of the images they collected, nine images were identified as being questionable and two were confirmed as being fake.

Whilst these studies demonstrate some of the positive and negative examples of the use of social media in crisis situations, it is necessary for partners to further examine new media usage across different types of crises. For instance, whilst some case studies such as that examining social media following the Boston attacks and Hurricane Sandy may show innovative and good practice in social media usage, others such as the 2013 UK heatwave demonstrate that social media were not effective. Accordingly examining a range of European and international case studies on the use of new media applications in different types of crisis situations will shed further light on lessons learned, which will be valuable to the overall objectives of the COSMIC project.

1.3 REPORT OUTLINE

The report will proceed with eight case study related chapters. Each chapter will focus on exploring the use of new media applications in a (previous) crisis situation. The selection of case studies includes both European and International case studies:

- Chapter 2: Boston attacks (2013)
- Chapter 3: UK heatwave (2013)
- Chapter 4: USA, hurricane Sandy (2012)
- Chapter 5: Haiti earthquake (2010)
- Chapter 6: Political crisis in Turkey (2013)
- Chapter 7: Colorado wildfires (2012)
- Chapter 8: UK floods (2012)
- Chapter 9: France, Storm Xynthia (2010)

In addition to examining the use of new media in each of these case studies, these chapters also explore how the use of new media might differ from other conventional uses of communication (e.g., radio and television broadcasting). Partners have also identified any

²⁰ Novak, J. M, and Vidoloff, K. G, “New Frames on Crisis: Citizen Journalism Changing the Dynamics of Crisis Communication”, *International Journal of Mass Emergencies and Disasters*, Vol. 29, No. 3, 2011, pp. 181–202.

²¹ Burgess, J., Vis, F. and Bruns, A, “How many fake Sandy pictures were really shared on social media?” *The Guardian Data Blog*, 6 November 2012.

lessons learned from these case studies for future crises, particularly in relation to how social media can be best used to satisfy different needs in a crisis.

The report will conclude in Chapter 10, by providing a summary of lessons learned as well as by identifying any possibilities and opportunities for the better use of social media in the future, which will also go some way to assisting the COSMIC project with providing guidelines and recommendations in work package 6 “Guidelines”.

2 BOSTON MARATHON BOMBING

The Boston Marathon is one of the USA's elite sporting events and one of the major marathons on the professional circuit. It is held annually on Patriot's Day, the third Monday of April, which is also a Massachusetts State Holiday. Children are off from school, banks are closed and many state offices are closed. On Monday, 15th April 2013, an estimated 23,000 people lined up at the start of the marathon.²² At approximately 2:50pm, two near-simultaneous explosions occurred near the finish line in downtown Boston. Three people were killed in the explosion and 264 runners and spectators were injured.²³ Paramedics, police and medical workers responded immediately to the crisis. The scene was cleared of all spectators and injured persons within 22 minutes, and the area around the blasts was cordoned off as a crime scene.²⁴ Immediately, the Boston Police Department, the Massachusetts State Police and the Federal Bureau of Investigation began a search for suspects. Those responsible for the attacks were identified using surveillance camera footage and images supplied by members of the public. Once identified, the suspects were killed or apprehended within 102 hours of the bombings after the city of Boston and the suburb of Watertown were placed on "lock down".

The explosions, the "lock down" and the search for suspects immediately became a lead news story around the world. While the vast majority of Americans (80%) followed the news story through traditional media, such as television, approximately half kept up-to-date via digital news and a significant minority, particularly younger people, kept up to date via social media sites.²⁵ In fact, "a majority of young people [those under 30] (56%) say they kept up with news and information about the bombings on social networks like Facebook and Twitter".²⁶ The technology blog *iRevolution* has celebrated this use of social media during disaster situations stating that:

Disasters are collective experiences; and today, disaster-affected crowds are increasingly 'digital crowds' as well—that is, both a source and consumer of that digital information. In other words, they are also the first *digital responders*.²⁷

²² Elgion, John and Micahel Cooper, "Blasts at Boston Marathon Kill 3 and Injure 100", *New York Times*, 15 April 2013.

²³ Kotz, Deborah, "Injury toll from Marathon bombs reduced to 264", *The Boston Globe*, 24 April 2013. <http://www.bostonglobe.com/lifestyle/health-wellness/2013/04/23/number-injured-marathon-bombing-revised-downward/NRpaz5mmvGquP7KMA6XsIK/story.html>

²⁴ Davis, Edward F. III, *Testimony Before the Senate Committee on Homeland Security*, US Senate, July 10, 2013.

²⁵ Pew Research Center, "Most Expect 'Occasional Acts of Terrorism' in the Future", 23 April 2013. <http://www.people-press.org/2013/04/23/most-expect-occasional-acts-of-terrorism-in-the-future/>

²⁶ *Ibid.*

²⁷ "Using Waze, Uber, AirBnB and SeeClickFix for Disaster Response", *iRevolution*, 11 June 2013. <http://irevolution.net/2013/06/11/uber-waze-airbnb-seeclickfix-for-disaster-response/>

The Boston Marathon Bombing was no different. Organisations and individuals used new information technologies to share information, including organising response to the disaster and coordinating efforts to find the suspects. Furthermore, members of the public used various social media tools and applications to follow and share information about the disaster, identify and locate suspects and provide assistance to those caught up in the event.

Consequently, the Boston Marathon bombing offers the COSMIC project an opportunity to study how new communication technologies and social media applications were utilised in a relatively recent event. This will enable COSMIC to examine the most recent developments in terms of technology and applications. It also provides the project the opportunity to study in detail a man-made disaster, which are like natural disasters in that they are often unexpected but also differ from natural disasters because they may often be preventable in a particular way. Finally, a case study of Boston Marathon bombing offers a comparison between European crisis management practices and responses and those of another context, i.e., the USA, which is also heavily infiltrated by ICT and social media use.

2.1 THE USE OF NEW COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND APPLICATIONS IN THE BOSTON MARATHON BOMBINGS

New communication technologies were primarily used by authorities to respond to the bombings, including the use of interoperable radio hardware, an Emergency Patient Tracking software tool and the Wireless Emergency Alert system. Each of these systems offered improvements on previous information and communication tools that authorities had at their disposal.

According to the Massachusetts Undersecretary for Homeland Security and Emergency Management, “interoperability was a success story” of the Boston authorities’ response.²⁸ In his initial assessment of the “lessons learned” as a result of the Boston Authority response, he stated that the investment in interoperability plans, radio channels, radio towers and new radios allowed “first responders, as well as command level personnel, to effectively communicate by radio between agencies, between disciplines, and between jurisdictions”.²⁹ This is an improvement over previous technologies used in crisis response, since landline telephone and cell phone usage, for example, would have been unreliable as both telephone systems “in the greater Boston area were overloaded by the spike in demand, rendering them largely inoperable”.³⁰

²⁸ Watson, Hayley, Rachel Finn, Kush Wadhwa and Angelos Yannopoulos, “State of the art of communication technology for crisis management”, *Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications*, COSMIC D2.1, 31 Aug 2013 also discusses interoperability as a key “need” in crisis management technologies.

²⁹ Schwartz, Kurt N., *Testimony before the Senate Committee on Homeland Security & Governmental Affairs: The Boston Marathon Bombings*, US Senate, 10 July 2013, p. 5.

³⁰ Ibid. See also a discussion on this in Watson, Hayley, Jelle Groenendaal, David De Vries and Alex Papadimitriou, *Report on Search and Rescue Operations*, COSMIC Deliverable 1.2, 30 September 2013.

Authorities also used a new software programme, the Emergency Patient Tracking System, to ensure that those injured were traceable and sent to appropriate medical facilities. According to the Deputy Administrator of the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), the tool is “a secure, web-based application that facilitates incident management, family reunification, and overall patient accountability during emergency incidents”.³¹ It allows authorities to collect demographic, healthcare, injury, age and gender information, which is recorded on a barcode worn as a wristband. Authorities can then:

view in real time the number of patients being treated at each location, their triage status and the number of patients who have been treated and released. This will help them make critical decisions, such as determining where to allocate additional resources.³²

The information is either transmitted to the hospital or “read” by the hospital once the patient arrives to facilitate effective treatment. It also ensures that particular hospitals are not overwhelmed with patients after an incident by spreading patients across area hospitals and ensuring that they are sent to the most appropriate facility (e.g., specialist burn units, etc.). This represents an improvement over previous practices, where a particular hospital would often be inundated with casualties due to its proximity to the site. In addition, because coordinators receive real time information about where each victim is receiving care, the system also can be used for family reunification.³³

Finally, the Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency (MEMA) also utilised Wireless Emergency Alerts (WEA), which are part of the FEMA Integrated Public Alert and Warning System (IPAWS).³⁴ WEA is an alert system that allows subscribed Emergency Management Agencies to push “geographically-targeted, text-like messages” to mobile phones in particular areas to alert them of “imminent threats to safety in their area”.³⁵ Individuals do not need to sign up to the service, but they must have a mobile phone that is WEA compatible, their service provider must be subscribed to the WEA system and they must be geographically located in the affected area. Major wireless carriers in the USA, such as T-Mobile, Verizon and AT&T are all signed up to the WEA service, as well as many other providers.

³¹ Serino, Richard, *Statement before the Committee on Homeland Security and Governmental Affairs: Lessons learned from the Boston Marathon Bombings: Preparing for and Responding to the Attack*, US Senate, 10 July 2013, p. 4.

³² Massachusetts Medical Reserve Corps, “Boston and Region 4 MRC Units Participate in 4th of July Patient Tracking Drill”, *Massachusetts Medical Reserve Corps Newsletter*, Fall 2008, p. 1. http://www.mamedicalreservecorps.org/newsletter/PDFs/MRC_Fall08.pdf

³³ Massachusetts Medical Reserve Corps, op. cit., 2008, p. 1.

³⁴ Schwartz, op. cit., 2013.

³⁵ Federal Communications Commission, “Wireless Emergency Alerts (WEA)”, Washington DC, 26 Feb 2013, p. 1. <http://transition.fcc.gov/cgb/consumerfacts/wea.pdf>

Furthermore, most new mobile phones are WEA compatible.³⁶ According to the Federal Communications Commission, this system is preferable to text message based emergency alerts, since this technology “ensures that emergency alerts will not get stuck in highly congested areas, which can happen with standard mobile voice and texting services.”³⁷ Significantly, members of the public further contributed to the efficacy of this system by using Twitter and other social media applications to share the WEA and amplify the message.

In addition to these new technologies and tools, both authorities and members of the public used social media applications to follow and respond to the crisis. The use of Twitter to amplify messages produced via new communication technologies points to some of the inter-linkages between new communication technologies and social media applications.

2.2 THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE BOSTON MARATHON BOMBINGS

According to Sutton, et al., the relay of messages on social media applications, such as Twitter, often falls into one of six different categories. These include:

- Advisories (e.g., advice about protecting oneself during the event)
- Closures or openings of specific services, public areas or transportation systems
- Hazard impact (e.g., number of casualties, resources utilised)
- Information about helplines, tips or preparedness
- Volunteer or donation information, and
- Other³⁸

Both authorities (including humanitarian organisations such as the American Red Cross) and members of the public used social media to follow the events, share information (e.g., alerts, advisories, closures, etc.) and respond to the crisis. Authorities largely focused on advisories, closures, hazard impact and providing information, but also used social media to solicit information from the public. Also, members of the public used social media to spread information (e.g., alerts, closures, police activities, etc.) across all five of these categories, and used it to respond to the crisis by searching for and identifying potential suspects. The use of social media by members of the public, however, carried particular risks, including wrongly identifying suspects and sharing confidential police information that could have endangered officers.

2.2.1 By authorities

³⁶ CITA: The Wireless Association, “Wireless Emergency Alerts on your mobile device”, no date. http://www.ctia.org/consumer_info/safety/index.cfm/AID/12082

³⁷ FCC, op. cit., 2013.

³⁸ Sutton, J., B. Johnson, E. Spiro and C. Butts, C., “Tweeting What Matters: Information, Advisories, and Alerts Following the Boston Marathon Events”, *Online Research Highlight*, 2013. <http://heroicproject.org>

The use of social media by authorities focused on established applications such as websites, Twitter and Facebook. COSMIC D2.1 *Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications* outlines six functions of social media in crisis situations:

1. One-way communication (notify/alert)
2. Two-way communication (converse/provide feedback)
3. Request/offer assistance
4. Relay (share a piece of information with others)
5. Campaign (awareness raising/fund raising)
6. Organise (co-ordinate response/enable individuals to organise themselves)³⁹

Authorities primarily used social media for one-way communication from authorities to members of the public and for two-way communication to solicit information from the public.

According to the Massachusetts Undersecretary for Homeland Security and Emergency Management, “local and state public safety and emergency management agencies effectively communicated with the public through social media[...]an emergency alerting Smart Phone app [...]and] the Wireless Emergency Alert Service”.⁴⁰ Furthermore, as stated above, the use of the WEA was a particular success story as individuals who received the WEA often used social media applications such as Twitter to amplify the message by re-tweeting the message and creating a “phone siren” effect (i.e., a message that is almost universally “heard”).⁴¹

Figure 3: Wireless Emergency Alert by Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency

³⁹ Watson, et al., “State of the art of communication technology for crisis management”, op. cit., 2013.

⁴⁰ Schwartz, op. cit., 2013, p. 5-6.

⁴¹ Galain, Rick, “Boston Bombing Shows How Wireless Emergency Alerts Can Work with Other Media”, *Emergency Management Blog*, 24 April 2013. <http://www.emergencymgmt.com/emergency-blogs/alerts/Boston-Bombing-Shows-How-042313.html>

The Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency also utilised the *Ping4alerts* system, a smartphone application, to send one-way instant alerts to iPhone and Android devices to alert individuals to situations and events happening in their area.⁴² The application is free to download. Alerts also appear on the Mass.gov homepage and on all executive agency websites.⁴³ These tools, and specifically the WEA and *Ping4alerts* represent an improvement on previous systems that relied upon broadcast media to disseminate information. Namely, such broadcast media often required individuals to be actively connected to receive the alert; and consequently, individuals who were not near televisions or not listening to the radio would be less likely to receive the information. In contrast, the WEA system and the smartphone application allow the authorities to push information to individuals, using a communication device that people have with them almost at all times, and that is almost always turned on (unless loss of battery prohibits a connection).

In addition to these systems, the Federal Bureau of Investigation engaged with crowdsourcing techniques to gain personal information about the suspects they had identified. First, authorities requested that premises near to the explosions share their private CCTV footage with the police. Second, the authorities also requested that members of the public who were at the event should share an images or video footage that they recorded.⁴⁴ This information was compiled and investigators identified two individuals as suspects. After erroneous speculation by mass media outlets and members of the public on social media (discussed further below), the FBI released the images of the two suspects and solicited public help in naming them.

Figure 4: FBI Press office tweet publicising suspect photos

The FBI shared the information with major news organisations who directed individuals to the FBI website, where members of the public could submit information.⁴⁵ Thus, while not a specific use of social media, the FBI website was transformed into a social platform that made use of crowdsourcing methods to identify the suspects. In a similar use of web resources, the American Red Cross encouraged people to “Register as Safe and Well” using their web database.⁴⁶ Families could also search the database to find out if a loved one had registered themselves. Google Person Finder also offered a similar service.

⁴² Mass.gov, “Get Emergency Information on Your Cellphone”, 2013. <http://www.mass.gov/eopss/agencies/mema/get-emergency-information-on-your-cellphone.html>

⁴³ Mass.Gov, “Mass.Gov Alert”, 2013. <http://www.mass.gov/alert/alertlanding.html>

⁴⁴ Ford, Bev, Greg B. Smith and Gary McShane, “Police Narrow in on Two Suspects in the Boston Marathon Bombing”, *New York Daily News*, 17 April 2013. <http://www.nydailynews.com/news/national/injury-toll-rises-marathon-massacre-article-1.1319080>

⁴⁵ Seelye, Katherine Q., Michael Cooper and Michael S. Schmidt, “F.B.I. Posts Images of Pair Suspected in Boston Attack”, *New York Times*, 18 April 2013. <http://www.nytimes.com/2013/04/19/us/fbi-releases-video-of-boston-bombing-suspects.html?pagewanted=all>

⁴⁶ American Red Cross, “American Red Cross Statement on Boston Marathon Explosions”, 15 April 2013. <http://www.redcross.org/news/press-release/American-Red-Cross-Statement-on-Boston-Marathon-Explosions>

Authorities and institutions also used more traditional social media platforms, such as Facebook and Twitter, to disseminate information to the public or gather information about the suspects. This included the Boston Police, the American Red Cross, the Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency, local universities and marathon organisers.⁴⁷ Social media was used in these instances to publicise alerts, to re-unite families, to publicise openings and closures and to share information.

Figure 5: Boston Marathon tweet sharing information about the bombing

The Boston Police used Twitter share the “shelter in place” warning and to announce the arrest of the suspect:

Figure 6: Boston Police Department "shelter in place" and “suspect in custody” tweets

Twitter and a popular Russian social networking site, VKontakte, were also utilised by police and journalists to gather information about the suspects. These tools as well as “favourites” listings on YouTube and a “wish list” on Amazon were thought to provide clues to the suspects’ personalities, interests and propensity for violence.⁴⁸

The social media droppings the Tsarnaev brothers left behind not only attest to their own immersion in the interactive, electronic world, but they have also provided everyone else with plenty of digital data from which to try to extract patterns and

⁴⁷ Sutton, et al., “Tweeting What Matters”, op. cit., 2013.

⁴⁸ Kakutani, Michiko, “Unraveling Boston Suspects’ Online Lives, Link by Link”, *New York Times*, 23 April 2013.

<http://www.nytimes.com/2013/04/24/us/unraveling-brothers-online-lives-link-by-link.html?pagewanted=all>

Books included on the Amazon wish list, for example Chechen history books, were thought to provide information about the suspect’s politics.

possible meaning — fulfilling that very human need to try to make narrative sense of the tragic and the overwhelming.⁴⁹

This use of social media in the investigation was thought to offer some indication of the suspects' state of mind and information about their social connections.

2.2.2 By members of the public

In addition to the use of these tools by authorities, members of the public also utilised popular social networking platforms for the following functions:

1. Two-way communication (converse/provide feedback)
2. Request/offer assistance
3. Relay (share a piece of information with others)
4. Campaign (awareness raising/money raising)

This included specifically, the use of social media to gather and share information, to post alerts, to pass along volunteer or donation information, and crucially in this case study, to attempt to identify and provide personal details of potential suspects.

Social media platforms such as Twitter and Facebook were heavily used by members of the public for a variety of different functions. According to Cassa, et al., messages on social media such as Twitter were recorded three minutes after the explosions, and were followed almost immediately by messages from public authorities.⁵⁰ In addition to Twitter, blogs were also used to document the events at the marathon as well as the police hunt for the suspects.⁵¹ However, experts warn that the lack of “a single hashtag, related to the weeklong investigation and subsequent manhunt and capture,” might have made it difficult for individuals to follow the different facets of the event from the explosions to the subsequent police search.⁵² Facebook, Google Docs and Twitter were also used to offer housing to those stranded in Boston after the marathon.⁵³ Reddit publicised these offerings and was also used to share information and resources such as advisories, closures and openings and information.

⁴⁹ Ibid.

⁵⁰ Cassa, C. A., R. Chunara, K. Mandl, J. S. Brownstein, “Twitter as a Sentinel in Emergency Situations: Lessons from the Boston Marathon Explosions”, *PLOS Currents Disasters*, 2 July 2013.

⁵¹ Hauser, Christine and Jennifer Preston, “After Boston Suspect’s Death, Social Media Fuel Conspiracy Theories”, *New York Times*, 25 April 2013. <http://thelede.blogs.nytimes.com/2013/04/25/after-boston-suspects-death-citizen-journalism-fuels-conspiracy-theories/>

⁵² Sutton, J., E. Spiro, B. Johnson, S. Fitzhugh and C. Butts, “Tweeting Boston: The Influence of Microstructure in Broadcasting Messages through Twitter”, *Online Research Highlight*, 2013. <http://heroicproject.org>.

⁵³ Karmon, Jennifer, “Boston residents open their homes after bombings”, *Yahoo.com*, 15 April 2013 and Mauriello, Tracie, “Congress wants to utilize social media during emergencies”, *Post-Gazette.com*, 5 June 5 2013. <http://www.post-gazette.com/stories/news/us/congress-wants-to-utilize-social-media-during-emergencies-690348/>

Figure 7: Reddit users share information about the bombing and offers of accommodation

Google analytics reported approximately 272,000 users on Reddit during the crisis with 85,000 in the news thread alone, indicating its increasing popularity.⁵⁴ Finally, Facebook was also used to publicise the existence of particular crowdfunding websites used by victims of the bombings to raise money to cover medical bills. Sites such as GoFundMe.com and GiveForward.com, as well as individual websites, helped raise money and allowed individual victims “a platform to tell their story”.⁵⁵ However, the public’s use of social media, and Reddit in particular came under fire for introducing specific risks during the crisis.

2.2.3 Risks and social media use

Although social media was utilised to share information and resources, and likely had a positive impact on the crisis, this information sharing also introduced specific risks into the crisis response, including principally the wrongful identification of suspects and the sharing of confidential police information that could have endangered officers.

Reddit, in particular, came under fire for its role in the wrongful identification of suspects during the police manhunt. This represents a particular, larger-scale risk of spreading misinformation, as well as tarnishing the reputation of identified individuals.⁵⁶ According to the media, Reddit users “turned into amateur sleuths” and wrongly identified a missing

⁵⁴ Martin, Erik, “Reflections on the Recent Boston Crisis”, *Reddit*, 22 April 2013. <http://blog.reddit.com/2013/04/reflections-on-recent-boston-crisis.html>

⁵⁵ Preston and Hauser, op. cit., 2013.

⁵⁶ Maron, Dina Fine, “How Social Media Is Changing Disaster Response”, *Scientific American*, 7 June 2013. <http://www.scientificamerican.com/article.cfm?id=how-social-media-is-changing-disaster-response>

student, Sunil Tripathi, as being one of the suspects, resulting in anguish for his family.⁵⁷ The manager of Reddit, Erik Martin, issued an official apology, citing that Reddit users had violated the site's ban on posting personal information.⁵⁸ However, Martin was unclear about how the spread of such information could be prevented in the future.⁵⁹ Maron warns that such incidents demonstrate that "there are no clear lines about who has responsibility to police social media information or how-or even if-that would work".⁶⁰ This is particularly problematic if information fits into a narrative that people want to believe.⁶¹ Social media were also implicated in the wrongful identification of two Boston men in the bombings, which in this particular instance, filtered into the mass media with the *New York Post* printing photos of the two men under the headline "Bag Men". The 16-year-old and the 25-year-old are both pursuing a lawsuit against the *New York Post* for "libel, negligent infliction of emotional distress, and invasion of privacy".⁶² In both cases, the *New Statesman* argues that the inter-linkage between social media and crowdsourcing "led to images stripped of their context being passed around as though they were confirmed".⁶³

Another risk associated with the use of social media by members of the public surrounds the sharing of confidential police information. Members of the public shared the locations of police officers as they moved around their neighbourhoods during the manhunt. They also listened to police radios via scanners and shared information about police activities. In both instances, officers warned residents, via Twitter, "Do Not Compromise Officer Safety by Broadcasting Tactical Positions of Homes Being Searched"⁶⁴ and to "stop disclosing information that could compromise the officers' search"⁶⁵.

In both these instances, the use of social media by members of the public either resulted in harm to specific individuals who were erroneously identified as suspects and potential harm to officers who were carrying out sensitive and dangerous public safety activities. In both cases, the affected individuals felt that their safety and security was threatened or

⁵⁷ Madrigal, Alexis, C., "It Wasn't Sunil Tripathi: The Anatomy of a Misinformation Disaster", *The Atlantic*, 19 April 2013. <http://www.theatlantic.com/technology/archive/2013/04/it-wasnt-sunil-tripathi-the-anatomy-of-a-misinformation-disaster/275155/>

⁵⁸ Martin, op. cit., 2013.

⁵⁹ Kaufman, Leslie, "Bombings Trip Up Reddit in Its Turn in Spotlight", *New York Times*, 28 April 2013. <http://www.nytimes.com/2013/04/29/business/media/bombings-trip-up-reddit-in-its-turn-in-spotlight.html>

⁶⁰ Maron, op. cit., 2013.

⁶¹ Madrigal, op. cit., 2013.

⁶² Sacchetti, Maria, "Mass. pair sues New York Post over Marathon bombing portrayal", *The Boston Globe*, 6 June 2013. <http://www.bostonglobe.com/metro/2013/06/05/libel-lawsuit-filed-against-new-york-post-bombing-coverage/enRvNI9PSig0AHDxJHYqFJ/story.html>

⁶³ Hern, Alex, "When crowdsourcing goes wrong: Reddit, Boston and missing student Sunil Tripathi", *New Statesman*, 19 April 2013. <http://www.newstatesman.com/world-affairs/2013/04/when-crowdsourcing-goes-wrong-reddit-boston-and-missing-student-sunil-tripathi>

⁶⁴ Cited in Sutton, et al., "Tweeting Boston", op. cit., 2013

⁶⁵ Cited in Buchanan, Emmilie, "Tragedy in the Time of Twitter: How social media expedites news during disaster", *Deseret News*, 28 May 2013. <http://www.deseretnews.com/article/865580777/Tragedy-in-the-time-of-Twitter-How-social-media-expedites-news-during-disasters.html>

compromised by social media activities which are often “anonymously posted” and which can be “difficult to correct or expunge once it has been cited by the media or shared extensively on social media platforms”.⁶⁶

2.3 LESSONS LEARNED

As discussed above, authorities identified early success stories in the use of new technologies and social media during the bombings, the immediate aftermath and the police manhunt, including communication interoperability, the Emergency Patient Tracking System, the use of WEAs and the use of social media as an additional public information platform. The Boston Police Commissioner reinforced the importance of having dedicated radio channels for communication as mobile phone services were ineffective because of volume from members of the public and satellite services presented difficulties when being used indoors or with multiple bodies.⁶⁷ He also asserted that the use of social media enabled “essential” communication with members of the public, including the use of Facebook and Twitter to stay connected with “residents, tourists and [the] business community”.⁶⁸ Particularly, this allowed the Boston PD to correct misinformation being circulated by members of the public and to share breaking news with the mass media.

Sutton et al. also describe how social media was a particular success in the aftermath of the bombing in that it allowed a “broader population” to follow the events including both local people and those significantly further away.⁶⁹ In their analysis of the use of Twitter in relation to the Boston Marathon bombings, they argue that different types of messages are relevant to different audiences and that organisations should “consider the kinds of information that is most desired by an online audience, at different points in time, and for different sectors of the public”.⁷⁰ Furthermore, inter-organisational network connections should be forged prior to an event so that organisations can amplify the messages being sent by one another to enable individuals to search for and confirm information.⁷¹

2.4 CONCLUSION

This case study has demonstrated how new communication technologies and social media applications were utilised in a recent, man-made disaster. It illustrates how new systems such as Wireless Emergency Alert systems, electronic Emergency Patient Tracking Systems and dedicated radio systems can assist authorities in sharing information with members of the

⁶⁶ Cassa, et al., 2013.

⁶⁷ Davis, op. cit., 2013, p. 6.

⁶⁸ Ibid., p. 4. See also Watson, et al., op. cit., *Report on search and rescue operations*, 2013.

⁶⁹ Sutton, et al., “Tweeting What Matters”, op. cit., 2013.

⁷⁰ Ibid.

⁷¹ Sutton, et al., “Tweeting Boston”, op. cit., 2013.

public, successfully managing medical response and communicating effectively with one another across different agencies. Furthermore, the use of social media, in particular, emerged as a key success story that allowed authorities, such as the Boston Police Department, to stay connected with members of the public, businesses and tourists and enabled the FBI to identify the suspects thanks to crowdsourcing methods. However, although the use of social media by members of the public amplified messages from authorities and enabled widespread information sharing, it also carried particular “risks” including endangering police officers conducting sensitive police duties and wrongly identifying individuals as suspects, leading to distress and other negative consequences.

3 UK HEATWAVE

The UK Meteorological Office (the Met Office), a government agency, considers a heatwave to be occurring once the temperature reaches a set level for three consecutive days. The heat levels vary by region, where, for example, the trigger temperature for North East England is 28C, while for London it is 32C.⁷² Overnight trigger temperatures range from 15C to 18C, again depending on region.⁷³ Once these levels are reached, the Met Office issues a heatwave alert. In July 2013 the UK experienced a heatwave that lasted approximately three weeks.

Heatwaves are considered a crisis for two different reasons. First, they trigger health-related effects. Older people, young babies and those with chronic diseases are susceptible to illness and/or death during heatwaves. For instance, in the 2003 heatwave, experts estimated that there were approximately 2,000 casualties in the UK, and around 30,000 in Europe as a whole.⁷⁴ Early estimates around the 2013 indicate that there may have been between 540 and 760 excess deaths in England and 60 to 100 excess deaths in Wales as a result of the heatwave.⁷⁵ However, these figures were questioned by journalists and experts, especially given that the data is not yet available and “heat” or “heatwave” are not listed as potential causes on death certificates.⁷⁶

Heatwaves are also considered a crisis because of their effects on the environment and infrastructure. Heatwaves can lead to increased pollution from manufacturing, energy and chemical plants⁷⁷ and can impact upon agriculture⁷⁸. Heatwaves can also trigger violent storms, flooding and forest fires, which can have cascading effects on homes, transport and critical infrastructure. For example, in the UK, at the peak of the heatwave which occurred between the 17 and 23 July, the dry temperatures led to storms which led to disruption for some train service providers. The Manchester Piccadilly train station, a major regional hub in the north of England, was struck by lightning, which caused major disruption to regional and national train services.⁷⁹ Additionally, storms caused disruption to power supplies in the east

⁷² “Heatwave: Health warnings issued for south-east England”, *BBC News*, 17 July 2013. <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-23341504>

⁷³ Ibid.

⁷⁴ United Nations Environment Programme, *Impacts of summer 2003 heat wave in Europe*, Environment Alert Bulletin, March 2004.

⁷⁵ Heatwave warnings extended to north-west England, *BBC News*, 20 July 2013. <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-23371454>

⁷⁶ Bland, Jessica, “Record heatwave deaths? It’s sunstroke I am worried about”, *The Guardian*, 19 July 2013. <http://www.theguardian.com/science/political-science/2013/jul/19/science-policy1> and Chalabi, Mona, “Will the heatwave kill us all?”, *The Guardian*, 18 July 2013. <http://www.theguardian.com/politics/reality-check/2013/jul/18/sun-heatwave-deaths-hot-weather>

⁷⁷ 18 July 2013 “Tata Steel, Port Talbot: Hot weather brings dust pollution for residents”, *BBC News*. <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-wales-south-west-wales-23351482>

⁷⁸ Carrington, Damian, “Heatwaves will make crops produce smaller grains”, *The Guardian*, 28 July 2013. <http://www.theguardian.com/environment/2013/jul/28/heatwaves-weather-farms-crops>

⁷⁹ “Manchester Piccadilly lightning strike disrupts trains”, *BBC News*, 23 July 2013. <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-england-manchester-23416589>

of England affecting power to homes, businesses, trains and the regional airport.⁸⁰ Finally, heatwaves can impact power supplies more directly, for example by affecting nuclear reactors that are cooled by river water.⁸¹

Given these multiple potential and observed impacts, the 2013 heatwave is a useful case study for COSMIC. First, it offers an example of a recent event and allows COSMIC to examine the technologies and applications that are currently available. Second, it is a crisis that enables a considered response in that responders and officials often have advanced warning of a heatwave, and it lasts for a number of days. Thus, unlike crises such as natural or man-made disasters, heatwaves do not require an emergency, immediate response. This may influence the types of technologies and social media utilised during the crisis as well as the ways in which it is utilised.

3.1 THE USE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE 2013 UK HEATWAVE

There was very little evidence of the use of new information and communication technologies during the 2013 UK heatwave. Instead, more established means of communication were used by authorities to spread messages about the heatwave alert and the associated health risks. The UK's national weather service, the Met Office, is charged with issuing heatwave warnings for England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland. There are four different levels of heatwave warning:

- **Green** – Summer preparedness and long term planning
- **Yellow** – Alert and readiness (Triggered at 60% or above of threshold temperatures, 30°C during the day and 15°C overnight, on at least two consecutive days and the intervening night)
- **Amber** – Heatwave action (Triggered when threshold is **reached** for one day and the following night, and the forecast for the next day has a greater than 90% confidence that the threshold temperature will be met. This stage requires social and healthcare services to target specific actions at high-risk groups.)
- **Red** – National emergency (Reached when a heatwave is so severe and/or prolonged that its effects extend outside the health and social care system. At this level, illness and death may occur among the fit and healthy, and not just in high-risk groups.)⁸²

The Met Office transmits these warnings to various organisations, including Public Health England, the National Health Service (NHS) and broadcast media (e.g., the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC)). This transmission of information primarily included

⁸⁰ “Storms disrupt trains and power supplies in East Anglia”, *BBC News*, 23 July 2013. <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-england-suffolk-23416428>

⁸¹ United Nations Environment Programme, *Impacts of summer 2003 heat wave in Europe*, Environment Alert Bulletin, March 2004.

⁸² Met Office, “Heat Health Watch”, no date. <http://www.metoffice.gov.uk/public/weather/heat-health/>

communication via e-mail and the web.⁸³ The national *Heatwave Plan for England 2013*, states that Public Health England would then use e-mail, the Internet, SMS messaging systems, television and radio broadcasts to disseminate warnings and health-related information to agencies and members of the public.⁸⁴ Presently, whilst news agencies such as the BBC included news updates⁸⁵ on their website regarding the heatwave, there is little (additional) information available about whether these agencies used other forms of communication during the crisis.

3.2 THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE 2103 UK HEATWAVE

COSMIC D2.1 *Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications* outlines six functions of social media in crisis situations:

1. One-way communication (notify/alert)
2. Two-way communication (converse/provide feedback)
3. Request/offer assistance
4. Relay (share a piece of information with others)
5. Campaign (awareness raising/fund raising)
6. Organise (co-ordinate response/enable individuals to organise themselves)⁸⁶

In response to the UK heatwave, social media was used by authorities and members of the public as forms of one-way and two-way communication to publicise the heatwave and distribute health-related information, as well as being used as a relay to share this information among organisations and individuals.

Although Public Health England primarily used established forms of communication, such as e-mail, television and radio, the 2013 *Heatwave Plan for England* states that this year social media feeds by the Met Office will be used to supplement this information.⁸⁷ An example of the Met Office Twitter feed is included below:

⁸³ Public Health England and NHS England, *Heatwave Plan for England 2013: Protecting health and reducing harm from severe heat and heatwaves*, May 2013.

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/201039/Heatwave-Main_Plan-2013.pdf

⁸⁴ Ibid.

⁸⁵ “Heatwave warnings extended in England”, *BBC*, 18 July 2013. <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-23355833>

⁸⁶ Watson, et al., op. cit., 2013.

⁸⁷ Public Health England and NHS England, *Heatwave Plan for England 2013: Protecting health and reducing harm from severe heat and heatwaves*, May 2013.

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/201039/Heatwave-Main_Plan-2013.pdf

Figure 8: Met Office heatwave Twitter feed

Here, the Met Office has publicised the heatwave warning and encouraged users to click on a website to find out more information. As shown in the figure above, the Met Office is also using Facebook, Flickr, YouTube, Google+ and Wordpress to disseminate information.

On Facebook, posts from the Met Office included images of maps of the UK containing temperatures, notifications of record highs of temperatures and links to health related warnings. As seen in the figure below, the health related post received 161 likes, 33 comments and 80 shares. Comments included general discussion on people enjoying the hot weather, to a comment that (sarcastically) questioned the use of warnings; “Do we really need warnings we survived without them before here's a clue if the sun is shining it could get hot you don't need to tell us”.⁸⁸

⁸⁸ Met office – Facebook page, July 2013. <https://www.facebook.com/metoffice>

Figure 9: Met Office - Facebook Page (2013)

The Met Office’s Google+ feed contained similar content including videos of the lightning strike, record temperatures and a link to tips from Cancer Research UK on keeping safe in the sun. The Met Office used the blog hosting site *Wordpress* to share a blog post about the heat wave, including links to health related information.

On YouTube, in collaboration with the CSO, Cancer Research UK, the Met Office profile, which has 5,419 subscribers, published videos relating to keeping safe in the sun, including staying safe from sun burn, what clothes to wear, how to avoid peak temperatures etc. The following table provides further information relating to the audience reception to these videos, interestingly those health related videos that were released at the beginning of the heat wave received a greater number of views than those published at the peak of the heatwave:

Table 2: The Met Office on YouTube during the 2013 UK heatwave

Video name	Date published	# of views	# of comments	# of shares
Cancer Research UK - Enjoy the sun safely	15 July 2013	1174	1	1
Is the UK having a heat wave?	17 July 2013	5786	41	6
Cancer Research UK - Sun safety tips	22 July 2013	103	0	0
Cancer Research UK Top Tips - Applying sunscreen	22 July 2013	187	0	0
Cancer Research UK Top Tips - The shadow rule	22 July 2013	303	0	2
Heavy thundery showers to	22 July 2013	8532	6	3

replace dry weather				
Lightning and rain from today's thunderstorms	23 July 2013	4798	9	3

Thus whilst platforms such as Google+ and Facebook contained similar content, the use of YouTube for sharing videos provided the Met Office with a unique platform to, collaboratively share visual based advisory content with audiences.

Finally, authorities, such as the NHS, and charities, such as AgeUK (the UK’s primary charity dedicated to the wellbeing of older people), used their webpages to issue guidance for vulnerable people – older people, the very young and those with chronic conditions – on how to stay cool. Visitors to the websites were often invited to download leaflets offering further advice. For instance, AgeUK prepared a leaflet “Staying cool in a heatwave” that advised people not only how to stay cool, but also how to avoid heatwave-related illnesses by avoiding strenuous activities, such as gardening and housework during those periods in the day that temperatures would be at their highest.⁸⁹

Other service organisations and crisis response organisations used social media to distribute information about the heatwave and to solicit information from the public. The London Resilience Team used their Twitter account, “London Prepared” to spread news about the temperature and the availability of free water in particular locations. Elsewhere, utility services, such as Water Direct, spread news via Twitter about the availability of free water. Transport companies, such as Virgin Trains, publicised the disruption caused by heat-related storms.

Figure 10: Virgin Trains tweet about train disruption

UK Power Networks, a British Utility company affected by the heatwave-related storms, also used social media as a form of two-way communication. They broadcast information about power outages, and they solicited information about power outages and vulnerable individuals from members of the public. Upon receiving notifications from members of the public, the UK Power Networks have been known to respond to them, engaging them in two-way communication (which is something they routinely participate in).

⁸⁹ “Staying cool in a heatwave: Tips to keep you cool when it’s very hot”, *AgeUK*, March 2013. http://www.ageuk.org.uk/Documents/EN-GB/Information-guides/AgeUKIL1_staying_cool_in_a_heatwave_inf.pdf?dtrk=true

Figure 11: UK Power Networks Tweet requesting information

As part of their service to members of the public during a power cut, they have also set up a text message based system that enable individuals to receive text based updates in the event of a power cut. Whilst they also utilise a number of other social networking applications (including Facebook, YouTube and LinkedIn), their use of social media to respond to enquiries seems to be conducted via Twitter only.

The British Red Cross also publicised heatwave-related information, particularly information about staying cool and preventing dehydration.

Figure 12: British Red Cross heatwave health warning

However, the excerpt from the British Red Cross Twitter feed indicates that there were very few re-tweets of these messages (less than 15). Furthermore, the UK Power Networks' message was only re-tweeted four times and the Virgin Trains messages were re-tweeted 19

and six times respectively. Consequently, there does not appear to be as much wide-spread information sharing from other social media users during this crisis as there was for other case studies examined in this report. Furthermore, these Twitter feeds indicate that re-tweets were primarily from individuals rather than “information brokers” or influential organisations or individuals (sometimes known as the “Twitterati”⁹⁰ due to their number of followers and relative influence). One exception is the UK Power Networks message which was re-tweeted by the Peterborough Telegraph, a regional newspaper. However, this lack of sharing of heatwave related information within major networks is not surprising given that most people will not be adversely affected by a heatwave that generates an Amber (level three) warning.

Some organisations, for example the British Red Cross, also used the hashtag “#heatwave” to link their messages to other heatwave-related information. However, the #heatwave hashtag was less useful in following news about the heatwave than expected. Many private companies used the hashtag to advertise sunglasses, book reading lists, ice cream parlours, and other goods and services, while individuals also used the hashtag to complain about the heatwave.

Figure 13: #Heatwave hashtag

Here, some organisations are using the crisis as an opportunity to advertise goods and services. Finally, the hashtag also included information about heatwaves in other locations, such as Germany, Belgium, China and the USA, making it difficult to use the hashtag to organise information about the events in the UK⁹¹. This means that vulnerable people looking to follow information about the heatwave as a crisis would have to sift through a number of superfluous pieces of information. However, despite this potential exploitative use of Twitter for advertising, most individuals were not adversely affected by this level of heatwave, meaning that the Twitter feed including commercial, personal and international information may have been useful or at least innocuous to those enjoying the warm weather.

⁹⁰ Singer, Natasha, “You’ve won a badge (and now we know all about you)”, *New York Times*, 4 February 2012.

⁹¹ Unless the user made use of the geo-tagging feature as part of the tweet.

In contrast, organisations and charities related to vulnerable people might be expected to carry significantly more information on the heatwave. Yet, the Twitter accounts of major charities for older people are primarily silent on the heatwave, and these organisations do not seem to be well integrated into social media networks. For example, AgeUK, a major charity focused on older people has a Twitter account, but did not author any tweets as of August 2013. AgeUK does, however, have a Facebook page, on which they posted the following information:

Figure 14: AgeUK Facebook heatwave warning

Unlike other social media messages, this AgeUK message, in particular, appears to be geared towards non-elderly people and encourages them to check on their neighbours. Diabetes UK, another charity focused on those who might be susceptible to the adverse effects of the heatwave, posted this on the 8th July:

Figure 15: Diabetes UK heatwave information

In both cases, these messages were not shared very widely. AgeUK has over 27,000 followers who “like” their Facebook page, yet their heat-related information was only shared by 76 people. Furthermore, Diabetes UK has over 52,000 “likes” and their information was only shared by 159 people. However, those who are vulnerable in heatwaves, e.g., older people, disabled people, etc., are also those who are least likely to use social media and new information and communication technologies.⁹² Specifically, according to the UK Office of National Statistics, people aged 65-74 are the least likely demographic to use social media - 19% of 65-74 year olds use social media compared to 90% of 16-24 year olds.⁹³ This suggests

⁹² Riga Declaration.

⁹³ Office of National Statistics, “Social Networking: The UK as a leader in Europe”, 13 June 2013. <http://www.ons.gov.uk/ons/rel/rdit2/internet-access---households-and-individuals/social-networking--the-uk-as-a-leader-in-europe/sty-social-networking-2012.html>

that first, the information about heatwave safety and vulnerability may not be reaching the correct individuals via social media and second, that those who are being reached by such messages are not reading them as relevant to their situation and may not relay them to others.

Finally, social media applications were used to share public health and safety information on the effects of the crisis. For example, the *BBC News* reports that Twitter was used to share the location of forest fires, enabling people to avoid affected areas.⁹⁴ In relation to public health effects, a *Guardian* journalist described how Google search data could be used to understand, and possibly predict, the prevalence of heat-related health problems such as sunstroke and heatstroke. The journalist found that searches for “sunstroke” and “heatstroke” increased during the heatwave in July, possibly indicating that more people were suffering from this condition. This information could be used as an additional data gathering tool in heatwaves to provide better evidence of the effects of the crisis.⁹⁵

Social media did have various functions during the 2013 heatwave in the UK. It was used by authorities, service organisations and charities to distribute messages about the heatwave and its health and other effects via one-way communication, and it was used by service organisations as a form of two-way communication to collect information from the public about vulnerable individuals and power outages. However, as a tool for relay, social media was less successful in distributing information among members of the public about the heatwave, as indicated by the number of “shares” and “re-tweets” these heatwave-related messages generated.

3.3 EFFICACY OF SOCIAL MEDIA

This information suggests that some organisations appear to have had a mixed success rate in terms of their use of social media to help respond to the crisis caused by the heatwave. Although some organisations utilised social media, these strategies were new or were often somewhat under-developed. However, the level of social media use, as well as general new technology use, is related to whether these technologies are commonly used in sub-populations that are most likely to be negatively affected during heatwaves, specifically older people, the very young and those with disabilities or long-term health conditions. This suggests that perhaps the continued use of more traditional media outlets remains appropriate to reach these vulnerable populations, especially during relatively minor heatwaves such as a level three. Instead, social media may be more appropriate for more severe heatwaves (level four) which are likely to affect the general population.

⁹⁴ “Epping Forest blaze under control”, *BBC News*, 19 July 2013. <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-england-london-23382771>

⁹⁵ Bland, Jessica, “Record heatwave deaths? It’s sunstroke I am worried about”, *The Guardian*, 19 July 2013. <http://www.theguardian.com/science/political-science/2013/jul/19/science-policy1>

Furthermore, even messages that encouraged those who were not affected by the heatwave to check on those who may be, were still not shared widely within social media applications. UK Power Networks asked members of the public to share information about vulnerable people who may be without power, while Age UK encouraged members of the public to check on older neighbours. However, in each case these messages did not appear to be widely relayed to others via Internet tools (they may have been shared offline). This phenomenon dampens some of the celebratory aspects of social media in crisis situations, where crisis-related messages that are deemed irrelevant by large proportions of the population are not widely circulated. Thus, it is not necessarily the most effective tool for all different types of crises.

3.4 LESSONS LEARNED

This case study also suggests a couple of lessons for future heatwaves. First, authorities and response organisations should continue to use traditional technologies and media alongside new technologies and social media to ensure that those who are most vulnerable, and least likely to use ICTs or social media receive the information they need. Cadot et al. stress that social isolation is a key risk-factor in vulnerability during heatwaves, and that older people, in particular, need to rely upon their social networks to ensure good health during heatwaves.⁹⁶ However, over-reliance on social media versus traditional communication methods may increase social isolation for those who do not use new technologies, and could adversely affect the most vulnerable during this type of crisis.

Second, this case study indicates a difficulty with using hashtags on Twitter to stay abreast of information and new developments. Specifically, those following developments using the “#heatwave” hashtag would have encountered a significant amount of extraneous information, including advertisements, personal commentary and international information. However, having a more detailed and less intuitive hashtag may not be as easy for users to find and may negatively impact information sharing. One potential possibility is for officials and major crisis responders (e.g., the British Red Cross) to agree upon a unique, but intuitive hashtags prior to major events in order to facilitate information sharing. For example, officials could decide in advance that crisis-related hashtags would be formed using the location, event and timeframe (e.g., #UKheatwave2013), creating both a unique and intuitive source of information.

⁹⁶ Cadot, Emmanuelle, Victor G. Rodwin, and Alfred Spira, “In the Heat of the Summer Lessons from the Heat Waves in Paris”, *Journal of Urban Health: Bulletin of the New York Academy of Medicine*, Vol. 84, No. 4, 2007, pp. 466-8.

3.5 CONCLUSION

In relation to other case studies examined in this report, the use of new communication technologies and social media was relatively light during the July 2013 UK heatwave. Official response organisations and agencies are beginning to use social media alongside more traditional communication mechanisms. However, the utility of these applications is constrained by the types of people using them, where the most vulnerable during medium-scale heatwaves are also the least likely to use social media. Furthermore, this crisis indicates that those who use social media cannot be depended upon to share information that is not relevant to their individual situation, thus indicating that authorities and crisis response organisations must consider their audience, their message and their medium of communication when integrating social media into their communication strategy. If it is beneficial to engage with the population at large to engage them in the further circulation of health related information to their wider social networks, particularly those that are most vulnerable to the threat posed by the heatwave, it is essential that organisations consider their message strategy so as to ensure that they appropriately gain the attention of those whom are not directly threatened in such a way as to engage them in further sharing their messages.

4 SANDY SUPERSTORM IN THE U.S.

After first hitting Jamaica, Cuba, Haiti, the Dominican Republic and Bermuda, a weakened Hurricane Sandy made landfall as a post-tropical cyclone in New Jersey with 70-kt maximum sustained winds,⁹⁷ on October 29, 2012. The geographical extent of the storm was huge – over the Atlantic, it reached a diameter of 1,800 km – and thus it had a massive effect coming over the New Jersey and New York coastlines. There were at least 72 direct deaths, and 75 indirect deaths in the U.S. Damage caused by the hurricane is estimated to have cost at least \$50 billion in the U.S.⁹⁸ This makes Sandy one of the six costliest cyclones to have hit the U.S. since 1900, and the deadliest outside of the southern states since Hurricane Agnes in 1972.

Figure 16: Path and size of Superstorm Sandy^{99,100}

In the U.S., government, organisations and citizens received several days' advance warning to prepare for the storm.^{101,102} The warning was met with considerable concerns by citizens,

⁹⁷ Blake, Eric S; Kimberlain, Todd B; Berg, Robert J; Cangialosi, John P; Beven II, John L; National Hurricane Center (February 12, 2013). Hurricane Sandy: October 22 – 29, 2012 (Tropical Cyclone Report). United States National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's National Weather Service.

⁹⁸ Hurricane/Post-Tropical Cyclone Sandy, October 22–29, 2012 (Service Assessment). United States National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's National Weather Service. May 2013. p. 10.

⁹⁹ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Sandy_2012_track.png

¹⁰⁰ https://www.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=424017394327705&set=a.131383016924479.23678.131370496925731&type=1&relevant_count=1

many of whom exhibited behaviours such as panic-buying of provisions.¹⁰³ The Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) co-ordinated the government response, with the President of the U.S. being directly involved in the process.^{104,105} Industrial organisations also prepared, in order to mitigate the risk of damages, and aiming to ensure a minimal disruption to their services.^{106,107} Social networks were used both in preparation and during the storm,¹⁰⁸ as detailed in the following sections.

Sandy in the U.S. is an interesting case study for the COSMIC project not only because it is a recent natural disaster hitting a technologically advanced region of the world but also because of its sheer extent: the regions influenced were large and highly populated (e.g., including New York city) and therefore we can study how the region's population as a whole reacted to the disaster. Sandy also saw a greater extent of Social Media use, by an "order of magnitude"¹⁰⁹, which makes it particularly interesting for COSMIC. In order to keep this report within reasonable size limits, we have chosen to focus on the time of preparation for and the time during Sandy, and on the U.S. experience of the storm.

4.1 THE USE OF NEW COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES DURING THE SANDY SUPERSTORM

New communication technologies played a significant role in the response to Sandy, ranging from modern two-way radio deployments, through mobile telephony technology, to novel web applications. Some representative examples are the following.

Interoperability was, as in many other crises, a significant issue. For instance, in New Jersey, with different government organisations and agencies urgently starting to co-ordinate shortly before the storm's arrival, a last-minute scramble was necessary in order to provide responders on the ground with interoperable communications – with multiple government agencies expected to converge on the area in response to the approaching disaster, the approach chosen involved the procurement of new equipment, to be distributed to personnel

¹⁰¹ Cisco, Jim (25 October 2012). "Extended Forecast Discussion – Issued 1342Z Oct 25, 2012". Hydrometeorological Prediction Center

¹⁰² Borenstein, Seth (25 October 2012), "Forecasters warn East Coast about 'Frankenstorm' next week; damage could top \$1 billion", The Washington Post

¹⁰³ Suzanne Goldenberg, "Washington DC shuts down in preparation for hurricane Sandy", The Guardian, Monday 29 October 2012

¹⁰⁴ "Closely Monitoring Hurricane Sandy". FEMA. October 25, 2012

¹⁰⁵ "It's watch and wait as Hurricane Sandy approaches". News.blogs.cnn.com. October 28, 2012

¹⁰⁶ American Petroleum Institute (API), "Oil and natural gas industry prepared for Hurricane Sandy", October 29, 2012

¹⁰⁷ Jean Kumagai, "Power Industry Faces Down Hurricane Sandy", IEEE Spectrum, October 30, 2012

¹⁰⁸ They were also used after the storm, e.g. to share experiences of the disaster, but this is not relevant to the present study

¹⁰⁹ Drake Baer, "As Sandy Became #Sandy, Emergency Services Got Social", Fast Company, November 9, 2012

requiring it, with the specific goal of providing interoperability; a high level of success was claimed.¹¹⁰

The Google Crisis Response team provided the Google Crisis Map, initially showing the location of the storm before landfall, and being enriched with progressively more information,¹¹¹ such as weather and observations, power outage information, shelters and recovery centers, aggregated local emergency twitter feeds, webcams, and more. “This map displays information about current crises and events for which the Google Crisis Response team has collected geographic information. The data comes from a variety of sources, including official information sources and user-generated content”.¹¹² This is a very interesting case as it shows a transition from new communication technologies to social media: initially, a state-of-the-art web-based map offers information integrated from weather services (category: new communication technologies) but rapidly it adds crowdsourced information (category: social media).

Figure 17: “Track Hurricane Sandy via Google's real-time crisis map”¹¹³

FEMA also utilised its Wireless Emergency Alerts (WEA),¹¹⁴ system, which, as described in section 2.1, «are part of the FEMA Integrated Public Alert and Warning System (IPAWS).¹¹⁵

4.2 THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA DURING THE SANDY SUPERSTORM

This section presents evidence of social media use during Superstorm Sandy. The following two sub-sections elaborate on social media use during preparation for the storm, and during the storm itself. However, we start, here, with some statistics showing the magnitude of social media usage in the context of Sandy.

¹¹⁰ Motorola, “Interoperability Helped New Jersey Weather Superstorm Sandy”, video report, <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DcVnZ0PKtNo>

¹¹¹ <http://queens.brownstoner.com/tag/fuel/>

¹¹² <http://google.org/crisismap/2012-sandy>

¹¹³ Philippa Warr, “Track Hurricane Sandy via Google's real-time crisis map”, WIRED, 29 OCTOBER 12

¹¹⁴ <http://abcnews.go.com/Technology/hurricane-sandy-wireless-emergency-alerts-people/story?id=17612492>

¹¹⁵ Schwartz, op. cit., 2013.

Figure 18 and Figure 19 show that Google searches relating Sandy to popular social networking sites were more popular than Google searches for FEMA or the U.S. President.

Figure 20 shows some additional statistics to demonstrate the relevance of the previous two figures: “Sandy” and “hurricane” are equally valid search terms to study (top), and they are highly “popular” even compared to the U.S. presidential elections (middle), while a comparison of “Fema” to combined searches for Sandy and social networks, which is possibly biased against the social networks, still leaves the social networks marginally ahead (bottom).

Figure 21 shows Twitter’s official report that there were 20 million tweets about Sandy

Figure 18: Google trends: sandy together with Twitter, Facebook, FEMA or Obama¹¹⁶

Figure 19: Google trends: hurricane together with Twitter, Facebook, FEMA or Obama¹¹⁷

¹¹⁶ <http://www.google.com/trends/explore?q=sandy+sandy#q=sandy%20twitter%2C%20sandy%20facebook%2C%20sandy%20fema%2C%20sandy%20obama&date=10%2F2012%202m&cmpt=q>

Figure 20: additional statistics to demonstrate the relevance of the previous two figures

Figure 21: Official statistics: 20 million tweets about Sandy¹¹⁸

4.2.1 Preparation

¹¹⁷ <http://www.google.com/trends/explore?q=hurricane+sandy#q=hurricane%20twitter%2C%20hurricane%20facebook%2C%20hurricane%20fema%2C%20hurricane%20obama&date=10%2F2012%202m&cmpt=q>
¹¹⁸ <https://twitter.com/twitter/status/264408082958934016>

Social Media were used in preparation for Superstorm Sandy hitting the U.S. Many organisations and individual responders used Twitter, including FEMA^{119,120} and the Maryland Emergency Management Agency¹²¹, and Facebook, including Hudson Valley Weather^{122,123}, to contact citizens in the affected region, informing them about the threat and providing information about measures that citizens should take before the storm arrives. For example, the Maryland Emergency Management Agency used Pinterest to disseminate easy to understand information, advice and instructions (Figure 7).¹²⁴ The use of striking pictures was a good idea for attracting the attention of people who would need to take the storm seriously, and prepare. Links to useful information were provided from the pictures.

Figure 22: Maryland Emergency Management Agency on Pinterest before Superstorm Sandy landfall¹²⁵ Information videos on YouTube were also a compelling way to capture the attention of people ahead of the disaster,¹²⁶ and to provide easy to understand information about preparing for the storm. A good example is social video for deaf people, who might otherwise have an increased difficulty in finding useful information.¹²⁷

4.2.2 During the storm

During Sandy, the affected populations took to the use of social media en masse (see for example the statistics in Figure 21, Figure 24, Figure 18, and Figure 19). Individual citizens of course used social media to communicate with each other, e.g. letting loved ones know about their safety and health status,¹²⁸ and social media were particularly useful to citizens as

¹¹⁹ <https://blog.twitter.com/2012/hurricane-sandy-resources-twitter>

¹²⁰ <https://twitter.com/FEMASandy>

¹²¹ <https://twitter.com/MDMEMA/status/262176945410826240>

¹²² Todd Essig, "How A Facebook Page Prepared A Region For Hurricane Sandy, And What That Teaches About Social Media", Forbes, October 29, 2012

¹²³ <https://www.facebook.com/HVWX1>

¹²⁴ <http://m.pinterest.com/mdmema/hurricane-sandy/>

¹²⁵ <http://idisaster.wordpress.com/2012/10/>

¹²⁶ www.youtube.com/watch?v=umLCdeBhLFk

¹²⁷ www.youtube.com/watch?v=uDkoQJ2h_cc

¹²⁸ Virtual Social Media Working Group and DHS First Responders Group, "Lessons Learned: Social Media and Hurricane Sandy", June 2013, U.S. Department of Homeland Security

a broadcast tool (a single post can be read by all “friends”/“followers”), with the key capability of being usable through mobile telephony networks even during a power and land-line outage.¹²⁹ While network outages and/or overload may often affect mobile telephony use during major emergencies, it should be noted that during Sandy Hurricane, mobile telephony networks were damaged but not altogether incapacitated.¹³⁰ However, an additional factor of key interest is that the practical utility of social media was catalysed by organisations and communities that provided tools and systematic assistance through these channels. Several examples follow.

The most fundamental kind of information during a weather disaster is weather information. During Sandy, people, including those suffering power outages but using mobile devices, could stay informed by receiving critical weather updates through social media such as Facebook and Twitter, and with Instagram and Pinterest surging in popularity for the sharing of information in image format.^{131,132} Such notifications addressed the weather itself (e.g., warnings of when exactly the storm would reach its greatest intensity), provided warning-messages urging citizens to seek shelter, and disseminated information about the impact of the weather, e.g. on damaged infrastructures.

Many organisations, such as the American Red Cross and the New York Fire Department, monitored social networks and were able to respond according to the information they were receiving from individuals^{133,134}: for example, by receiving emergency requests for help, and by learning about areas seriously affected by the disaster, e.g. with power outages, flooded roads, or downed power lines. The role of the Red Cross Digital Command Center, which focuses on monitoring social media, was significant enough for the centre to receive a personal visit by the U.S. President.

¹²⁹ David W. Boles, "Smartphone Battery Management During Hurricane Sandy", November 6, 2012, bolesblogs.com

¹³⁰ Federal Communications Commission, "Statement From David Turetsky Regarding Communications Network Improvements And Restoration", November 2, 2012

¹³¹ www.accuweather.com/en/weather-news/social-media-and-hurricanes-disasters/9550752

¹³² <http://www.continuityinsights.com/blogs/2013/07/digital-lessons-learned-superstorm-sandy>

¹³³ <http://news.yahoo.com/blogs/ticket/meet-fdny-one-womantwitter-response-team-guiding-141143449.html>

¹³⁴ “Dell solutions provide the Red Cross with innovative ways to help Americans impacted by disaster”, video and case study available at <http://www.dell.com/learn/us/en/uscorp1/corp-comm/red-cross-digital-operations>

Figure 23: October 30, 2012, President Barack Obama visits the American Red Cross Digital Command Center following Hurricane Sandy¹³⁵

The Google Crisis Map, described above, by incorporating citizen-generated information, as a form of crowdsourcing, transitioned from an application of “new communication technologies” to an application of “social media”.

4.3 RISKS AND SOCIAL MEDIA USE

Social media were used during Sandy, as has also been the case on other occasions,¹³⁶ to spread rumours and falsehoods. FEMA set up a page that specifically deals with this issue.¹³⁷ Citizens around the world contributed to an effort to distinguish real images from false ones,¹³⁸ however it is not clear to what extent they were successful. Real images can provide government and citizen responders with valuable information about the situation on the ground; thus, false information, even if created humorously or frivolously, can have serious and dangerous consequences in practice, by misleading citizens as well as responders.

Fraud is recognised as a threat during and after all disasters, but social media contributed to “modern” forms in the case of Sandy, such as bogus donation requests via social media.^{139,140,141,142} Requests posted via social media can present easy-to-use payment methods, but, in order to avoid fraud, citizens must independently verify the validity of the request, and ideally make a payment through a more trusted channel, as advertised via official, verifiable communication of the charity or other entity requesting assistance.

¹³⁵ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:RedCross_Obama_1.jpg

¹³⁶ http://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/aug/27/rim-fire-california-social-media-avoid?CMP=twf_fd

¹³⁷ <http://www.fema.gov/hurricane-sandy-rumor-control>

¹³⁸ www.istwitterwrong.tumblr.com

¹³⁹ <http://nj.gov/oag/ca/stopsandyfraud/>

¹⁴⁰ <http://www.aarp.org/money/scams-fraud/info-11-2012/hurricane-sandy-scams.html>

¹⁴¹ http://www.nj.com/news/index.ssf/2013/02/founders_of_hurricane_sandy_ch.html

¹⁴² <http://longisland.about.com/od/governmentschools/a/How-To-Donate-Responsibly-And-Avoid-Hurricane-Sandy-Scams.htm>

Another key issue in use (and potential misuse) of social media pertains to utilisation of social media, rather than conventional channels such as calling the emergency phone line 911, to report emergency information. The following case is illuminating:¹⁴³

Throughout Sandy, the New York Fire Department (FDNY) provided information through the official department Twitter feed¹⁴⁴. Early on, FDNY's social media manager, Emily Rahimi, posted directions not to tweet emergency calls. However, as the storm progressed, individuals tweeted calls for help, reporting flooding, individuals trapped in buildings, and more. FDNY responded to these calls, asking for more information, contacting dispatch and relaying information regarding the individuals' posts, and assisted when individuals were not able to get through to 911.¹⁴⁵

We can see that the New York Fire Department expected citizens to use social networks for emergency calls, but it initially considered this an incorrect practice, since a call to 911 will be dealt with systematically by the correct government organisation, whereas e.g. a Tweet may easily be ignored. However, 911 was overwhelmed during Sandy. On this occasion, by monitoring Twitter, the New York Fire Department was able to provide additional support. However, there clearly remains a risk, in the case of future disasters, of citizens channelling emergency calls through social media and not receiving assistance. The success of social media in this example case may increase the risk if proper measures are not taken to address the heightened use of social media for reporting emergencies. On the one hand, educating citizens to always use official channels for emergency calls unless they are unavailable may be needed. Also, emergency response organisations should systematically improve procedures needed to respond to emergency calls made through social media.

4.4 LESSONS LEARNED

We have seen that social media can play a key role during a weather disaster. Telecommunications infrastructures and services may suffer outages during a disaster – some affected citizens may have an operational land-line but no data network connectivity, while for others the reverse may be true thanks to cable or mobile data connections. In the case of Sandy, many people relied specifically on social networks as a key communication tool, sometimes supplanting traditional communication channels, such as 911 (the emergency telephone number), which was congested. They sent, received or shared a variety of information, including weather reports, news, personal information about themselves or loved ones, instructions, and making emergency requests for help. The key lessons include:

- Even when there are alternative and potentially more proper means of communication, people will use social media. Responders must monitor social media

¹⁴³ Virtual Social Media Working Group and DHS First Responders Group, "Lessons Learned: Social Media and Hurricane Sandy", June 2013, U.S. Department of Homeland Security

¹⁴⁴ <https://twitter.com/FDNY>

¹⁴⁵ <http://news.yahoo.com/blogs/ticket/meet-fdny-one-womantwitter-response-team-guiding-141143449.html>

in order to be informed of the situation, and can use social media themselves to disseminate important information.

- The information available through social media is extremely rich and plentiful, and can be used to analyse the situation during an ongoing disaster.
- Social media will prove to be the most effective communications tool available to some citizens, depending on the particular problems (such as power or service outages) affecting them.
- Different modalities of communication are becoming important, especially with users sharing vast numbers of photographs, in addition to text and voice communications.
- Crisis maps, especially when enriched through crowdsourcing approaches with information aggregated from social media communications, are very powerful tools.
- There are also significant risks involved in the use of social media. Social media may be used for the dissemination of deceitful, fraudulent, incorrect or misleading information. Also, important information can be sent through social media, but fail to be received by appropriate responders.

Indeed, Sandy marked a step increase in the level of significance that social media played, compared to previous natural disasters in the U.S. We have seen that many significant actors in the disaster made significant use of social media. This can be contrasted with previous examples where the use of social media was important, but nevertheless more incidental¹⁴⁶ – for example in the case of Hurricane Irene, “a few agencies, already using live data within a mapping environment, began including tweets from response agencies within the impact zone as an additional data layer. The information collected from social media (or crowd-sourced data), however, imposed a specific concern; the information was not vetted or verified and therefore was not used for more than informational purposes”.¹⁴⁷

Finally, it is important that these “lessons learned” are being learned not just in popular or academic circles, but also by aid agencies and governments. In the wake of Sandy we find, for example, the U.S. Department of Homeland Security documenting “Technology, Process, and Policy Gaps Requiring Further Discussion”,¹⁴⁸ which is in effect an initiation of the process of serious requirements emerging, being formalised, and eventually being met, for social media as a crisis management tool, as there is an emerging need to use social media as mission-critical grade telecommunications systems.¹⁴⁹

¹⁴⁶ <http://www.thehomelandsecurityblog.com/2011/09/23/engaging-citizens-the-right-way-governmentuses-twitter-during-hurricane-irene/>

¹⁴⁷ Virtual Social Media Working Group and DHS First Responders Group, "Lessons Learned: Social Media and Hurricane Sandy", June 2013, U.S. Department of Homeland Security

¹⁴⁸ Virtual Social Media Working Group and DHS First Responders Group, "Lessons Learned: Social Media and Hurricane Sandy", June 2013, U.S. Department of Homeland Security

¹⁴⁹ Mission-critical grade telecommunications systems are telecommunications systems that can be relied upon in cases where their correct functioning is an essential requirement for a successful operation. For example, mission-critical grade telecommunications systems must provide rugged devices capable of functioning in an unfavourable environment, e.g. in the rain or at very high temperatures. Other definitions: mission-critical: (of hardware or software) vital to the functioning of an organization

4.5 CONCLUSION

This case study has demonstrated that social media are now an important, indispensable, powerful and, indeed, irrevocably relevant communications tool in the context of crisis management. Social media are not, currently, mission-critical grade telecommunications systems, but they are often relied upon heavily and they are often extremely useful, therefore researchers and governments should work towards graduating social media to the highest reliability and criticality levels of service. In the meanwhile, of course, users should be aware of their limitations, and consider (complementary) alternatives such as more traditional telephony and data services for their crisis communication needs.

In conclusion, we provide some additional, interesting statistics on Hurricane Sandy:

[<http://oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/mission--critical>]; Definition of 'Mission Critical': An activity, device, service or system whose failure or disruption will cause a failure in business operations
[<http://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/mission-critical.asp>]

Case Spotlight: 2012 Hurricane Sandy

(Fitzgerald, 2012; Kurtz & Look, 2012; Prakash, 2012)

BACKGROUND: From October 29-30, 2012 a category one hurricane swept across the U.S. East Coast causing eight states to declare states of emergency and resulting in up to \$50 billion in damage.

MEDIA USE FINDINGS:

- **The public flocked to the Internet** with the East Coast’s Internet usage increasing 114% the first day of the storm.
- **Twitter was a key venue for information sharing** with 1.1 million people mentioning the word “hurricane” on Twitter within a 21-hour time period.
- **Twitter also served as a key venue for misinformation.** For example, photos of soldiers at Arlington Cemetery that went viral were taken in September, not during the storm. Also, another viral photo of clouds over New York City was photoshopped.
- **Facebook was another key venue for information sharing.** Sandy became the number two most talked about topic on Facebook during 2012.
- For the first time the photo-sharing site **Instagram played a major role in information sharing** during a disaster with ten storm-related pictures per second posted on the site.
- **The public turned to Internet-based telephone services to connect** with friends and loved ones after the disaster; Skype alone received a 122% spike in traffic after the storm.

Figure 24: Statistics on Sandy and Social Networks¹⁵⁰

¹⁵⁰ Fraustino, Julia Daisy, Brooke Liu and Yan Jin. “Social Media Use during Disasters: A Review of the Knowledge Base and Gaps,” Final Report to Human Factors/Behavioral Sciences Division, Science and Technology Directorate, U.S. Department of Homeland Security, College Park, MD: START, 2012.

5 HAITI EARTHQUAKE

On January 12, 2010, a 7.0Mw earthquake struck Haiti, a poor Caribbean country. The epicentre was near the capital city of Port-au-Prince. The death toll of at least 100,000 (Note: the death toll is disputed; claims range from 100,000 to over 300,000^{151,152}), together with 300,000 injured and 1,500,000 people left without shelter, makes this one of the most damaging earthquakes on record, indeed far worse than the 7.0Mw magnitude might lead one to expect. The shallow depth of the earthquake, and the poor construction of many buildings in the region, which Bilham characterised as “buildings [...] designed to kill their occupants”, contributed to the extreme devastation.¹⁵³ The earthquake caused additional damaging side effects, including a Tsunami¹⁵⁴ and an outbreak of Cholera.¹⁵⁵

The 2010 Haiti earthquake is an interesting case study for COSMIC because it is a recent event, its consequences and the aid effort that responded to them were extensive, it represents an economically poor part of the world (the COSMIC case studies have made a representative selection of different profiles of affected populations), and it precipitated a higher level of social media engagement than previously seen in the case of a natural disaster.

Figure 25: Pictures of the damage caused by the 2010 Haiti earthquake, taken from social media^{156,157,158,159}

¹⁵¹ Columbia Journalism Review, *Two Years Later, Haitian Earthquake Death Toll in Dispute*, Jan. 20, 2012

¹⁵² http://earthquake.usgs.gov/earthquakes/world/most_destructive.php

¹⁵³ Bilham, Roger. "Lessons from the Haiti earthquake." *Nature* 463.7283 (2010): 878-879.

¹⁵⁴ "Lessons to be learned from Haiti's tsunami", BBC News, 25 February 2010

¹⁵⁵ "Haiti's cholera deaths increase", Al Jazeera English, 31 December 2010

¹⁵⁶ (top-left) <https://picasaweb.google.com/lh/photo/EJoLQ1-ICoKKd0-Ukroj9MTjNZETYmyPJy0liipFm0>

5.1 THE USE OF NEW COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE HAITI EARTHQUAKE

New communication technologies played an important role in the response to the 2010 Haiti earthquake. Some representative examples are provided in this section.

Communication infrastructures in the area affected by the earthquake were severely damaged. Traditional telecommunication technologies such as television broadcasting and land-line telephony were destroyed, or rendered inoperable due to the power outage also caused by the earthquake, to such an extent that communication between Haiti and the rest of the world using traditional communication technologies was nearly impossible for 24 hours after the earthquake.^{160,161} The mobile telephony network was also severely damaged¹⁶² – 70% of the infrastructure was initially destroyed – and yet it was this technology that offered the best communications opportunity initially: the infrastructure was rapidly repaired, the damage caused a severe degradation but not a full black-out of the mobile telecommunications service, and connectivity to the internet via mobile phones remained possible.¹⁶³ Local radio broadcasts were also possible, and it is characteristic that a key piece of information broadcast over radio was information to survivors on how best to use their mobile phones to respond to the situation¹⁶⁴.

A simple example of the use of “new communication technologies” was Skype, which was often the only way to enable voice communications shortly after the earthquake.¹⁶⁵ Consequently, early interviews of survivors by international mainstream media organisations were conducted through Skype.

In addition, within 48 hours of the earthquake, InSTEDD (Innovative Support To Emergencies, Diseases and Disasters¹⁶⁶) and Thomson Reuters set up the EIS project¹⁶⁷ (Emergency Information Service) to enable communication to and from the disaster survivors.

¹⁵⁷ (top-right) https://picasaweb.google.com/lh/photo/e12FjSME2EojmP_oE0Mu9tMTjNZETYmyPJy0liipFm0

¹⁵⁸ (bottom-left) <http://www.flickr.com/photos/oxfamnewzealand/4286901626/>

¹⁵⁹ (bottom-right) <http://www.flickr.com/photos/handicapinternationaluk/6771230309>

¹⁶⁰ “The Haitian News Vacuum”, Columbia Journalism Review, 13 January 2010 (http://www.cjr.org/the_kicker/the_haitian_news_vacuum_1.php)

¹⁶¹ Nelson A., Sigal Ivan with Dean Zambrano, “Media, Information Systems and Communities: Lessons from Haiti”, 2010

¹⁶² “Crowdsourcing Crisis Information in Disaster Affected Haiti”, Special Report by United States Institute of Peace, October 2010 (<http://www.usip.org/publications/crowdsourcing-crisisinformation-in-disaster-affected-haiti>)

¹⁶³ “Cell phones and radios help save lives after Haiti earthquake”, Reuters, 2010, <http://www.reuters.com/article/2010/01/25/us-haiti-telecoms-idUSTRE60007M20100125>

¹⁶⁴ “Cell phones and radios help save lives after Haiti earthquake”, Reuters, 2010, <http://www.reuters.com/article/2010/01/25/us-haiti-telecoms-idUSTRE60007M20100125>

¹⁶⁵ “New Media Vital in breaking Haiti earthquake story”, BBC World Agenda, 22 January 2010 (http://www.bbc.co.uk/worldservice/worldagenda/2010/01/100122_worldagenda_haiti_monitoring.shtml).

¹⁶⁶ <http://instedd.org/about-us/>

¹⁶⁷ <http://www.reuters.com/article/idUSTRE60G16420100117>

EIS, using SMS, enabled Haitians to report missing persons, shelter problems and food issues, while the service also sent SMS texts with important information to registered users. Comcel and Digicel (as major Haitian Telcos) offered the service for free. The service integrated successfully with Ushahidi, discussed below, as well as with aid organisations on the ground, such as the Red Cross. It is interesting that Ushahidi, which as a crowdsourcing application can be classified as social media, drew valuable information from EIS, which is in the new communications category – thus, we see that such technologies are clearly capable of interoperating.

Figure 26: The 4636 service, thanks to a partnership between the Emergency Information Service (EIS), InSTEDD, Ushahidi, Haitian Telcos and the US State Department¹⁶⁸

Finally, the International Charter on Space and Major Disasters^{169,170} was activated in the wake of the disaster, allowing satellite imagery of affected regions to be shared with rescue and aid organisations.¹⁷¹ Using satellites facilitated the discovery of vital information, such as identifying which roads and bridges were damaged and which were still intact, which remote areas had suffered the worst damage, and where refugee camps could best be set up.

¹⁶⁸ “Ushahidi & The Unprecedented Role of SMS in Disaster Response”, <http://irevolution.net/2010/02>

¹⁶⁹ <http://www.disasterscharter.org/home>

¹⁷⁰ http://www.disasterscharter.org/web/charter/activation_details?p_r_p_1415474252_assetId=ACT-287

¹⁷¹ Amos, Jonathan, “How satellites are being used in Haiti”, BBC News, 14 January 2010. (<http://www.bbc.co.uk/blogs/thereporters/jonathanamos/2010/01/how-satellites-are-being-used.shtml>)

5.2 THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE HAITI EARTHQUAKE

5.2.1 Connectivity Statistics

Before discussing social media usage in the case of the 2010 Haiti earthquake, it is instructive to consider the statistics of the Haitian population's connectivity to telecommunications services.

Figure 27 shows mobile cellular subscriptions (per 100 people) in Haiti (1995-2012). Figure 28 shows Internet users as a percentage of population in Haiti (1995-2012). Figure 29 shows fixed broadband Internet subscribers (per 100 people) in Haiti (2001-2011). Figure 18 shows telephone lines (per 100 people) in Haiti (1981-2012).¹⁷²

We can clearly see that the penetration of mobile telephony is far ahead of other means of communication in Haiti, with the 2010 level having been 40 subscriptions per 100 people, compared to an 8% internet connectivity, and very low 0.16% broadband penetration and 0.5% telephone line penetration. Looking at the trends, we can see

- telephone line penetration actually falling rapidly as of 2006-2007, when mobile telephony was getting a firm foothold;
- internet access being strongly correlated to mobile subscriptions, although remaining at significantly lower levels;
- and broadband access seems a negligible quantity as far as the broader population is concerned.

In this context, the observed widespread services based on SMS, and difficult but not impossible access to the internet, during the disaster, should not be surprising.

Figure 27: Mobile cellular subscriptions (per 100 people) in Haiti (1995-2012)

¹⁷² <http://data.worldbank.org/>

Figure 28: Internet users as a percentage of population in Haiti (1995-2012)

Figure 29: Fixed broadband Internet subscribers (per 100 people) in Haiti (2001-2011)

Figure 30: Telephone lines (per 100 people) in Haiti (1981-2012)

5.2.2 Social media and the response to the earthquake

In the immediate aftermath of the earthquake, traditional telecommunication technologies such as television broadcasting and land-line telephony were almost completely inoperable. Nevertheless, Haitians made contact with the outside world almost immediately, with twitter users including @FredoDupoux,¹⁷³ reporting on the status of Port-au-Prince within minutes of the earthquake commencing. Haitians also used twitter to communicate with each other. For example, the same user urged survivors to help one another in the following tweet: “It’s really ugly, just like in a bad dream. people need help, get out and help ! #haiti @eq”.

Twitter was the first social media outlet used, it remained heavily used throughout the aftermath of the disaster, and its use was widely publicised.^{174,175,176} Nevertheless, many other social media were taken up soon afterwards, including Facebook, YouTube, iReport, Flickr and Skype.^{177,178,179,180} Facebook and TwitPic (a service for sharing photos and videos on Twitter) enabled the publication of the first pictures of the earthquake’s effects, while YouTube and iReport provided the first videos.

Organisations such as the American Red Cross turned to social media to raise donations in order to aid Haiti. With the Haiti earthquake being one of the most communicated issues on social networks, millions of dollars of aid money were raised through social campaigns.^{181,182} NGOs and charities made particularly strong use of Twitter to provide news, raise awareness, and solicit aid contributions worldwide, ranging from Doctors Without Borders to the United Nations.^{183,184}

¹⁷³ <https://twitter.com/FredoDupoux>,

¹⁷⁴ Ingram, Matthew, “Twitter: the first draft of history?” (<http://www.mathewingram.com/work/2008/05/12/twitter-the-first-draft-of-history/>)

¹⁷⁵ Smith, Brian G. "Socially distributing public relations: Twitter, Haiti, and interactivity in social media." *Public Relations Review* 36.4 (2010): 329-335.

¹⁷⁶ “Social Media and Mobile Texting a Major Source of Info and Aid for Earthquake in Haiti”, NielsenWire, 15 January 2010 (http://blog.nielsen.com/nielsenwire/online_mobile/social-media-and-mobile-texting-amajor-source-of-info-and-aid-for-earthquake-in-haiti/).

¹⁷⁷ <http://blog.facebook.com/blog.php?post=466369142130>

¹⁷⁸ Muralidharan, Sidharth, et al. "Hope for Haiti: An analysis of Facebook and Twitter usage during the earthquake relief efforts." *Public Relations Review* 37.2 (2011): 175-177.

¹⁷⁹ “New Media Vital in breaking Haiti earthquake story”, BBC World Agenda, 22 January 2010 (http://www.bbc.co.uk/worldservice/worldagenda/2010/01/100122_worldagenda_haiti_monitoring.shtml).

¹⁸⁰ Yates, Dave, and Scott Paquette. "Emergency knowledge management and social media technologies: A case study of the 2010 Haitian earthquake." *International Journal of Information Management* 31.1 (2011): 6-13.

¹⁸¹ “Burst of Mobile Giving Adds Millions in Relief Funds”, New York Times, 14 January 2010 (<http://www.nytimes.com/2010/01/15/technology/15mobile.html>)

¹⁸² “Haitian Earthquake Dominates Twitter”, Sysomos Blog, 15 January 2010 (<http://blog.sysomos.com/2010/01/15/haitian-earthquake-dominates-twitter/>).

¹⁸³ www.twitter.com/MSF_USA

¹⁸⁴ www.twitter.com/UNHaitiInfo

Crowdsourcing based on social media also played a significant role. The social media provided a huge flow of unorganised, unverified information. Crowdsourcing efforts aggregated, organised and (to a lesser extent) vetted this information, while also providing valuable services such as displaying aggregate information on maps, and providing feeds of organised information to responders on the ground. Examples of such efforts included the Ushahidi Haiti Project^{185,186} and iReport.¹⁸⁷ The information being shared over social media often included urgent messages such as reports of injuries or of trapped people, as well as expressing important needs for instance regarding food and shelter. It was widely recognised that crowdsourcing helped organise first responders on the ground, to deal with needs according to relevance and urgency. For example, in the U.S., the Secretary of State, the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) and USAID recognised this contribution.¹⁸⁸

Figure 31: Short code created for free reporting of emergency info and location by SMS texting (advertisement)¹⁸⁹

¹⁸⁵ Morrow, Nathan, et al. "Independent evaluation of the Ushahidi Haiti project." Development Information Systems International 8 (2011).

¹⁸⁶ <http://haiti.ushahidi.com/>

¹⁸⁷ "New Media Vital in breaking Haiti earthquake story", BBC World Agenda, 22 January 2010 (http://www.bbc.co.uk/worldservice/worldagenda/2010/01/100122_worldagenda_haiti_monitoring.shtml).

¹⁸⁸ <http://blog.ushahidi.com/2010/02/06/ushahidi-how-we-are-doing/>

¹⁸⁹ <http://blog.ushahidi.com/2010/01/17/the-4636-sms-shortcode-for-reporting-in-haiti>

Figure 32: Ushahidi map example¹⁹⁰

Figure 33: Ushahidi map example¹⁹¹

Social media were also used to exert political pressure and open challenging communication lines. For example:

¹⁹⁰ “Software that helps populations cope with crises”,
<http://www2.technologyreview.com/TR35/Profile.aspx?TRID=947>

¹⁹¹ “Software that helps populations cope with crises”,
<http://www2.technologyreview.com/TR35/Profile.aspx?TRID=947>

“Jason Cone, Doctors Without Borders’ communications director, explained that after Haiti was struck by a devastating earthquake, the U.S. military assumed control of Haiti’s airfield in Port-Au-Prince and began prioritizing incoming flights. Doctors Without Borders tried to send a team of physicians to Haiti to assist the wounded, but they were unable to get clearance to land. Cone issued a press release about the dilemma — but he also explained the problem via Twitter. [Ann] Curry saw Cone’s tweets and took up the cause. Eventually, she was able to establish offline contact with Pentagon officials and convince them to allow the Doctors Without Borders flight to land. Twitter is “our best option – maybe our first option from now on” for getting a message out during a crisis, Cone said.”¹⁹²

Ann Curry’s tweet “@usairforce find a way to let Doctors without Borders planes land in Haiti: <http://bit.ly/8hYZOK> THE most effective at this.” was selected by Twitter as the most powerful tweet of 2010,¹⁹³ as it influenced the decision making of the U.S. Air Force in Haiti during the crisis.

Finally, it is worth mentioning a lost opportunity: a capability that social media offered, but that was not exploited:

“A July 2012 study demonstrated that real-time monitoring of Twitter messages in Haiti could have predicted the October/November 2010 cholera outbreaks two weeks earlier than they were detected. Anonymised data, shared by Digicel, demonstrated that population movements in response to the cholera outbreak began prior to official detection of the outbreak. Deaths from cholera are preventable and outbreaks are more easily dealt with in their early stages. This means there was a lost opportunity to save lives. While there is no way to arrive at a precise statistic, over 200 people had died by 23 October, four days after first detection, and 900 by 16 November. Overall, more than 6,000 people died and over 400,000 became ill”

and although this was an important missed opportunity, in the future such information can be exploited successfully.^{194,195,196}

5.3 RISKS AND SOCIAL MEDIA USE

As described in chapter 4: “Fraud is recognised as a threat during and after all disasters, but social media contributed to “modern” forms in the case of the 2010 Haiti earthquake, for

¹⁹² <http://smartblogs.com/social-media/2010/02/02/how-twitter-saved-lives-in-haiti/>

¹⁹³ <https://2010.twitter.com/powerful-tweets/>

¹⁹⁴ Humanitarianism in the Network Age: Including World Humanitarian Data and Trends 2012, Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), 2013.

¹⁹⁵ Hirschfeld, D. Twitter data accurately tracked Haiti cholera outbreak. Available from <http://www.nature.com/news/twitter-data-accurately-tracked-haiti-choleraoutbreak-1.9770>.

¹⁹⁶ Chunara R, Andrews JR, Brownstein JS. Social and news media enable estimation of epidemiological patterns early in the 2010 Haitian cholera outbreak. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 2012;86:39-45

example bogus donation requests via social media»^{197,198,199}. Requests posted via social media can present easy-to-use payment methods, but, in order to avoid fraud, citizens must independently verify the validity of the request, and ideally make a payment through a more trusted channel, as advertised via official, verifiable communication of the charity or other entity requesting assistance.”

Another risk in the use of social media for crisis communications and management, which indeed materialised in the case of the 2010 Haiti earthquake, is that of invalid information being circulated²⁰⁰ – whether accidentally or by malicious intent. For example, users were widely re-tweeting false claims that UPS offered free shipping to Haiti and that certain airlines were offering free flights to doctors volunteering to go to Haiti. The misinformation resulted in the respective companies receiving a great volume of communication about these supposed offers, which disrupted their operations.

A particularly interesting issue is the response of mainstream news organisations to the misinformation problem.²⁰¹ Mainstream media are under great pressure to deliver timely reports. However, with social media breaking news within minutes of events occurring, the ability of mainstream media to ascertain the validity of content arriving from social media is small (while their own reporters will not be able to always be on-the-spot when, where and as major events occur). Thus, they are under pressure to use social media as sources, as fast as possible, while at the same time being aware that verifying the incoming information is difficult. There is a real risk of mainstream media erring on the side of speed rather than correctness and accuracy.

5.4 LESSONS LEARNED

Several important lessons can be learned from studying the 2010 Haiti earthquake case:

- Journalists henceforth take on an active role assisting and participating in the efforts of first responders. The critical difference, compared to the past, is that now agility, speed, intuition and good sourcing of information about the crisis have become a critical dimension of any large-scale aid effort. Thanks to social media, information that can enable a great improvement in the effectiveness of an aid effort is available. However, the breadth of information, its real-time nature and unreliability makes the available information very difficult to process and creates a need to interact with

¹⁹⁷ <http://blogs.wsj.com/digits/2010/01/20/social-networking-carries-haiti-earthquake-fund-raising-into-another-week/>

¹⁹⁸ http://www.npr.org/blogs/tellmemore/2010/01/haiti_needs_help_swindlers_on.html

¹⁹⁹ <http://redtape.msnbc.com/2010/01/fake-fundraising-efforts-for-the-haiti-disaster-are-spreading-like-wildfire-on-facebook-dozens-of-fan-pages-have-been-set-up.html#posts>

²⁰⁰ “Haiti: False Rumors on the Twittersphere”, *Foreign Policy*, 14 January 2010 (http://blog.foreignpolicy.com/posts/2010/01/14/false_rumors_on_the_twittersphere).

²⁰¹ Nic Gowing, “Skyful of Lies and Black Swans. The new tyranny of shifting information power in crisis”, *Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism Challenges*, 2009, p. 28.

sources so as to elicit more or better information for key issues. Through their ability to deal with this challenge, journalists acquire a new role actively participating in a humanitarian effort, even though traditionally their role is supposed to be that of a detached observer not involved in intervention and participation.

- Social media usage can be aggregated to discover information not present in individual messages. Aggregates provide information ranging from *which* topics are trending, to tracking or recognising the movements or patterns of movement of large numbers of individuals. In this respect, it is useful to distinguish between aggregating the actual content of social media messages, and aggregating the “data exhaust”^{202, 203, 204} generated by usage of social media.
- Social media can be a very valuable, and potentially the only, source of information about an afflicted population during a crisis.
- Social media can offer a powerful means of two-way communication between survivors and responders, providing information about needs and problems in real-time, with geo-localisation, and enabling a conversation to explore and best meet urgent or emerging needs.
- Social media provide “raw” news, which is also of interest to the global public, who can directly monitor the reports coming from eye-witnesses on the ground during a crisis, and also from the victims themselves.
- Social media are a powerful tool for raising awareness and donations to aid crisis-stricken populations.
- Certain populations may have better access to social media than to more traditional telecommunications services. Also, social media may remain functional when traditional telecommunications services black out. Thus, social media may be used out of necessity during a crisis, not (only) out of choice.

5.5 CONCLUSION

This case study has demonstrated that social media are now an important, indispensable, powerful and, indeed, irrevocably relevant communications tool in the context of crisis management. They may be the only communications tool available during a crisis, and in any case they are a highly usable and rich communications tool – therefore, their popularity in crisis management can only be expected to grow. At the same time, social media pose various

²⁰² Deloitte, "The power of zoom: Transforming government through location intelligence", GovLab (http://www.deloitte.com/assets/Dcom-SouthAfrica/Local%20Assets/Documents/power_of_zoom_report.pdf)

²⁰³ O'Hara, Kieron, Mischa M. Tuffield, and Nigel Shadbolt. "Lifeloggging: Privacy and empowerment with memories for life." *Identity in the Information Society* 1.1 (2008): 155-172.

²⁰⁴ Data exhaust consists of information generated as a side-effect of users' activities, which is an indirect form of communication (comparable to body language as another indirect form of communication, but here in the context of ICT). Whereas social media *messages* consist of communication explicitly and intentionally communicated by social media users (e.g. a tweet asking for help), data exhaust is a digital record of people's interactions with digital technologies (e.g. when a mobile telephony provider records the location of a mobile phone user – which in crisis management could be used e.g. to produce an estimate of the minimum number of people known to have been at the ground zero of a major disaster).

risks, such as messages not being seen by the correct responders, misinformation being spread with verification being particularly difficult, and fraud being committed through social media. Thus, it remains interesting to see how populations continue to use social media in response to crisis, and how technology and organisations help to improve the effects of using social media in this context.

6 GEZI PARK PROTESTS IN TURKEY

Recent reports from Reporters without Borders indicate that, as of 2013, Turkey ranks 154th out of 179 countries in terms of press freedom.²⁰⁵ While press freedom in Turkey has always been problematic, particularly since the 1990's, consolidation of media has led to a significant decrease in availability of diverse news/information sources. Since the current ruling party (*Ak Parti*) came to power in the 2002 national elections in Turkey, press freedom, and media bias have become heavily debated issues. Critics have frequently argued that during *Ak Parti*'s tenure, political pressure on the press has increased and that the mainstream media have been quickly (re)configured to create what critics named as “*yandaş*” (a derogatory term that is used to describe uncritical-partisanship of *Ak Parti*) media.²⁰⁶

It is within this context of heightened monopolization of the media in Turkey that the use of social media during the *Gezi Protests* becomes a key case study for understanding the role that social media play in political crises. *Gezi Protests* started in May 28th 2013 as a relatively small sit-in protest against removal of trees for the new redevelopment project in Taksim square area and *Gezi Park* (located in Taksim Square area). Following the violent eviction of the protestors from the *Gezi Park*, the protests quickly spread around Turkey and the agenda of the protestors quickly evolved to include not only the redevelopment project in Taksim but also issues such as the increased encroachment of the ruling party in the private lives of the citizens, threats to freedom of speech, freedom of assembly, and freedom of the press. The supporters of the protest movement were highly vocal about the lack of and bias in coverage of the protests (figure below).

Figure 34 – (On the left) A vandalized news truck of NTV, a news channel that was criticized for biased coverage of the protests. The spray paint writings on the truck read “for sale” “false news”, “sold-out bastards.”²⁰⁷ (On the right) The Turkish affiliate of CNN, CNNTURK, was also criticized for airing a documentary about penguins rather than providing breaking news about the protests.²⁰⁸

²⁰⁵ Reporters without Borders. “Press Freedom Index.” Paris, 2013. <http://en.rsf.org/press-freedom-index-2013,1054.html>

²⁰⁶ For a summary of these debates, Çarkoğlu, Ali, Lemi Baruh and Kerem Yıldırım. “Echo Chambers in Election Coverage: Campaign Advertisements, Newspapers’ Readership Base, and Press-Party Parallelism in Turkey.” Paper presented at the *Annual Meeting of the IAMCR*. Dublin, Ireland, 2013.

²⁰⁷ Uludağ Sözlük Galeri. “Taksim’deki NTV Yayın Aracı.” 2013. <http://galeri.uludagsozluk.com/g/taksim-deki-ntv-yay%C4%B1n-arac%C4%B1/>

²⁰⁸ “Redhack’ten CNN Türk’e Tavsiye!” *GazeteCell*. 3 June 2013.

In other words, for many of the protestors and opposition groups supporting the protestors, internet and social media were considered to be the major, if not the only, outlet through which they could be informed about the protests and voice their opinions. In considering the potential role that the Internet and social media may have played during the Gezi protests in Turkey, it should be noted the Internet penetration in Turkey is considerably lower than the average Internet penetration in European Union. Yet, Internet penetration has been steadily increasing. According to a recent report by the Interactive Advertising Bureau, within the last year, percent of population (older than 12) with Internet access has increased by %4 to reach 44%; and 57% of people who have access to Internet use it daily.²⁰⁹ In addition, according to the Turkish Statistical Institute, among the young adults population (aged between 18-25), the Internet penetration rate is 67.7% (however, there seems to be a considerable gender gap with 80% of males and 55% of females having access to Internet).²¹⁰

In this chapter, after a brief discussion of the use of communication technologies during Gezi Protests (6.2) the partners will summarize the results of a survey that was conducted in June 2013 regarding the use of social media in general, and Twitter in particular, during the Gezi Protests in Turkey. Section 6.3 will outline the procedures related to the survey (6.3). Next, the report will first focus on (6.4) utilization of news sources (including mass media and social media sources) before and during Gezi Parkı protests. The section to follow (6.5) will summarize the findings from an open-ended question regarding why respondents used social media during the protests. Finally (6.6) the report will provide a detailed analysis of how Twitter was utilized during the protests.

Consequently, the Gezi Protests offers the COSMIC project an opportunity to study how new communication technologies and, more specifically, social media applications were utilised in a recent political crisis during which the structure of the mass media market is seen by many citizens as a symptom (and a factor contributing to) the crisis. This will enable COSMIC to examine how and for what purposes individuals utilize social media applications. It also provides the project the opportunity to compare and contrast how mass media and social media are used at times of political crises.

6.1 THE USE OF COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES DURING GEZI PROTESTS

It should first be noted that unlike most of the other emergencies (e.g., Haiti Earthquake, Hurricane Sandy) that the case studies in Deliverable 2.2 focus on, the protests did not cause severe (or widespread) damage in information and communication infrastructure. However,

<http://www.gazetecell.com/medya/redhackten-cnn-turke-tavsiye-h50792.html>

²⁰⁹ Cited in Aydın, Batuhan, “Türkiye İnternet Kullanıcı Sayısı: 26.6 Milyon [IAB Türkiye Şubat 2013]”, *eticaretmag*, 19 April 2013.

<http://eticaretmag.com/turkiye-internet-kullanici-sayisi-26-6-milyon-iab-turkiye-subat-2013/>

²¹⁰ Türkiye İstatistik Kurumu, “İstatistiklerle Gençlik, 2012”. 17 May 2013.

<http://www.tuik.gov.tr/PreHaberBultenleri.do?id=13509>

there were still instances when infrastructure was strained due to overload and physical damage.

For example, early reports claimed that the government utilized jammers to disable mobile telephony communications and compelled ISPs and 3G connection providers to cut down the bandwidth of Internet connections.²¹¹ However, these claims remained unverified and were denied by major ISPs and 3G connection providers, which reported that the slow connections were due to a strain on the Internet infrastructure.²¹²

Such an overload on both mobile telephony networks and Internet connections should not be surprising given the scale of the protests and the fact that protestors often relied on a mix of technologies that could strain the connections. A news report on the use of these different technologies underline how protestors switched between different modes of connection while trying to establish a constant stream of information among themselves as well as publicizing information to the larger public. According to this report:²¹³

- In addition to use of social media, such as Facebook and Twitter, which will be discussed in more detail in the remainder of this chapter, protestors frequently utilized Google and Yahoo e-mail groups to communicate with each other.
- Likewise, SMS applications such as Whatsapp were used to form information networks. Accordingly, particularly at times when Twitter slowed down due to overload in networks, these applications, as well as conventional SMS messaging, were used to send information to users abroad so that they could Tweet the information to wider circles.
- Live streaming services like Livestream and Ustream were used by citizen journalists to provide real time coverage the protests.
- For constant real-time communication, handheld transceiver (i.e., walkie-talkie) services provided by mobile telephony service providers and applications, like Zello, which emulate handheld transceiver functions for smartphones were utilized.
- Google Maps was utilized to mark the locations of nearby healthcare facilities, pharmacies, open Wifi hotspots, shelters.

During the protests, another issue that was debated was the availability of CCTV footage from protest areas. Particularly in Istanbul, live streaming of CCTV cameras is used for informing drivers about congestions in traffic. During the protests, as with Internet and mobile telephony services, initial unverified reports claimed that the government shut down the live streams from CCTV cameras from areas near Taksim square. The Minister of Interior, Mr. Muammer Güler, quickly denied the claims, reporting that the streams stopped because

²¹¹ “Valilik’ten Gezi Parkı’na Sinyal Kesici Jammer”, *Habere Dikkat*. 31 May 2013.

<http://www.haberedikkat.com/Haberler/79342/valilikten-gezi-parkina-sinyal-kesici-jammer>

²¹² Kaplanselen, Erdal, “Gezi Sebebiyle İnternette Engelleme-yavaşlatma Oldu Mu?”, *Hürriyet*. 5 June 2013.

<http://www.hurriyet.com.tr/pasaj/23440397.asp>

²¹³ İnce, Elif, “Ya internetler kesilirse... Gezi Parkı'nın teknoloji uzmanları anlattı!", *Radikal*. 5 June 2013.

http://www.radikal.com.tr/turkiye/ya_internetler_kesilirse_gezi_parkinin_teknoloji_uzmanlari_anlattı-1136386

the cameras were damaged during the protests.²¹⁴ However, in a later incident, involving the death of a protestor named Ethem Sarısülük, it was observed that the CCTV camera, which was originally oriented towards the area where Mr. Sarısülük was shot by a police officer, first turned away from the area and then focused on a tree. In the light of such incidents, as will be described later in this report, citizen reporting of police activities, and usage of streaming services and social media to disseminate video recordings regarding police activities, was of crucial importance for protestors.

Finally, with respect to use of ICTs during the Gezi protests, reports also indicate that the protestors actively tried to decrease the capacity of security officials to coordinate by interfering with the police radio frequencies. Despite being an effective strategy to counter police interventions, such interference in police radio frequencies may also potentially undermine emergency communications and may compromise the safety of both civilians and police.

6.2 PROCEDURES AND PARTICIPANTS

The survey was fielded online by COSMIC partner Koç University between June 10th and June 29th. Respondents were recruited via invitations, sent via e-mail, blogs, Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn. Therefore, we can make no claim about the representativeness of the survey results.

At the beginning of the survey, all respondents were informed that the survey was anonymous, they had the right to refuse participation, right to not answer a specific question and terminate the survey at any time. Individuals younger than 18 were not allowed to participate in the survey.

Out of 890 respondents who started the survey, 329 completed it. On average, the survey lasted for 15 minutes. Respondents were predominantly female (64%). The reported mean age of the respondents was 28 (SD = 9.2). A majority of the respondents (54%) indicated that they were still students at a higher education institution (undergraduate or graduate). On average, the respondents reported using the Internet for about 4 hours per day for purposes other than school or work. More than half of them reported visiting news websites at least once a day (69%), do instant messaging for at least once a day (60%), visit video sharing sites (58%), use Facebook (77%). A considerably smaller percentage of the respondents reported using the Internet at least once a day for writing blogs (13%) and participating in discussion forums (13%). A majority of the respondents were Twitter users before the Gezi Parkı protests (85%).

It should be noted that the respondents of this survey were in many ways more similar to respondents to surveys conducted^{215 216} on Gezi protestors than it was to citizens who

²¹⁴ “MOBESE’ler Kapatıldı İddialarına Cevap Verdi”, *Dünya*. 4 Haziran 2013.

<http://www.dunya.com/mobeseler-kapatildi-iddilarina-cevap-verdi-194093h.htm>

²¹⁵ “Diren Gezi Parkı Anketi 3000 Kişi Tarafından Yanıtlandı”, *Avrupa Gazete*. 5 June 2013.

<http://www.avrupagazete.com/haberler/13609-diren-gezi-parki-anketi-3000-kisi-tarafindan-yanitlandi.html>

supported the Turkish governments' response to the protests. About 70% of the respondents reported leaning left on a 10-point political ideology scale. Also, more than 50% of the respondents reported having voted for the main opposition party CHP and 15% reported having voted for the left leaning Kurdish political party (BDP) in the previous national elections. Finally, about 70% of the respondents had previously signed a petition, 50% of the respondents reported that they had previously participated in protests, and 50% had previously boycotted a brand or a company. In this respect, the partners believe that although the survey is not representative of the population or the protestors, the findings from the survey is more likely to be indicative of the social media usage patterns of Gezi Parkı protestors than the rest of the population.

6.3 NEWS SOURCES BEFORE AND DURING GEZI PROTESTS

In order to compare and contrast the utilization of news sources before and during the Gezi Protests, respondents were asked to complete two sets of questions that inquired about whether they used printed newspapers, websites of newspapers, other websites, social media (including Facebook and Twitter), television, radio, and word of mouth (radio and word of mouth were later combined for analysis) 1) on a “typical” day and 2) during the first three weeks of the Gezi Protests.

As it can be seen from Figure 35, overall, the respondents preferred online sources (websites of newspapers and social media) to conventional sources such as television, printed newspapers and other sources, which included radio and word of mouth.

Regarding the respective use of online sources in a typical day and during Gezi protests, results summarized in Figure 1 suggest that during the events respondents quickly moved away from online sources associated with established mainstream sources and started utilizing social media. Whereas 49% of the respondents reported using websites of newspapers for news during a typical day, only 6% reported using them during the Gezi Protests. At the same time, 85% of respondents reported using social media during the Gezi Protests (compared to 35% during a typical day).

²¹⁶ “Gezi Anketinden İlginç Sonuçlar”, *Haberturk*. 13 June 2013.
<http://www.haberturk.com/gundem/haber/852023-gezi-anketinden-ilginç-sonuclar>

Figure 35: News Consumption: Typical Day vs. During Gezi Protests.

6.4 SOCIAL MEDIA USE MOTIVATIONS DURING GEZI PROTESTS

An open-ended question inquired about why respondents relied on social media during the Gezi Protests. Typically each respondent provided one main reason for using social media during Gezi Protests; however, a considerable number of respondents gave two or three reasons. These open-ended responses were coded using grounded theory.²¹⁷ Each response was coded for as many reasons as a respondent provided.

Accordingly, 57% of the respondents indicated that they relied on social media during the Gezi Protests to get up to date, real time information about what was happening in Taksim Square (the ground zero of the protests) and elsewhere in Turkey (Figure 36). Also, 10% of the respondents reported that via social media they were able to get first-hand information from peers who were actively participating in the protests. For example, according to one respondent, use of social media was important because “Everybody could share what they experienced and their feelings instantly. It allowed me to learn in real time the needs of the protestors, what needed to be done, what events transpired in which location.” Likewise, another indicated that “the only way to attain true information was to get it first hand from people” and at many times social media, despite issues regarding reliability of information, “were the **only** source of information.”

Relatedly, and more specifically, close to 40% of the respondents indicated that they did not trust the mainstream mass media for coverage of the protests. Namely, 23% indicated that they did not think mass media paid sufficient attention to the protests and 16% commented that they thought the mass media coverage was biased. For example, one respondent indicated that she did not want to be exposed to the misinformation from mainstream media because

²¹⁷ Corbin, Juliet, and Anselm Strauss, *Basics of Qualitative Research: Grounded Theory Procedures and Techniques, ... Theory Procedures and Techniques*, Sage Publications, London, 1990.

“whether national or international, small or large, content from all mainstream media was influenced by political and financial interests. Hence, I did not want to be exposed to their information *poison*.” Also, a considerable number of respondents indicated that initially, they relied on mainstream media; however, after witnessing the lack of coverage and the bias in existing coverage, they had no choice but to utilize social media to get information about the protests.

Indeed, in terms of reliability, 13% of the respondents indicated that they found “crowdsourced” information from social media to be more reliable than information in mass media. It should be noted that this comment by respondents was more often than not qualified with statements regarding their awareness of prevalence of misinformation on social media. However, respondents indicated that they knew how to filter misinformation. Deliverable 2.3 will discuss in further detail how the survey respondents filtered misinformation.

Figure 36 also details other key uses of social media. For example, in addition to getting up to date information about what was happening during the protests, social media were also used by respondents to learn about the opinion of the public (gauge public opinion = 13%). The open ended answers suggest that for only a small minority of these respondents, social media was about learning about the opinion of people who did not think like themselves.

Also, respondents reported that social media were the only way through which they could voice their opinion and raise awareness of others about what was transpiring in the protests. For example, many respondents considered voicing opinions in social media as a responsibility:

“The protest was not just a simple incident; it was an environmental, social, political, legal, economic “phenomenon”. In the light of the violent suppression of even the most fundamental democratic rights, I could not have been quiet. It was my duty as an urban citizen to take action to protect the culture of the city, to protect our rights, and our shared future.” (Anonymous Respondent)

“I think that everybody needs to hear about the injustice out there. I wanted to be informed about the events and I wanted to disseminate information. This lack of justice makes my heart ache and I don’t know what else to do. The mass media are lying, politicians are lying, and when I look at Twitter, I see I am not alone.” (Anonymous Respondent)

In terms of the relationship between social media use and participation in the protests, two answers stood out. First, 13% of the respondents indicated that by learning about the events, where police were organized, and where people were being injured, they could mobilize and provide assistance to the protestors. Second, even if not actively participating in the protests, 7% of the respondents cited social media as a venue through which they could feel and communicate “comradery” with the protestors.

Figure 36: Reasons for Utilizing Social Media During Gezi Protests

6.5 TWITTER USE DURING GEZI PROTESTS

94% of the respondents reported having visited Twitter to tweet or to read tweets about Gezi Protests. During the protests, on average, respondents spent about 2.5 hours per day on Twitter and logged into their Twitter accounts for about 8 times per day. Slightly more than half of the respondents (53%) used their smart phones to access Twitter during the protests. This was followed by personal computers (37%) and tablets (10%). All respondents reported either using their web browsers or the Twitter app for reaching Twitter. The two other applications that were used, albeit with very low frequency, were Hootsuite (1%) and Tweetdeck (3%).

Respondents were then asked to complete two questions, which used a 9-point scale, to indicate the extent to which they would categorize their use of Twitter during Gezi Protests as oriented towards...

- 1) “voicing your opinions” (1) . . . “share news/updates” (9)
- 2) “sharing updates/opinions” (1) . . . “following updates/news from others” (9)

For both questions, about 30% of the respondents categorized themselves as being right between the two opposites. Respondents were more likely to categorize themselves as using Twitter to learn about opinions/updates from other people (45.6%) than sharing their own opinions about the protests (23%).

A two-step cluster analysis was performed on the answers to these two questions to identify segments of users who have distinct Twitter utilization orientations. The results of this cluster analysis revealed four segments of Twitter users (Figure 37).

1. **Update Seekers:** This segment comprised users who overwhelmingly reported using Twitter for news/updates (73.5%) and for learning about what others have shared (100%) rather than sharing something themselves (0%).
2. **Update Hubs:** Close to half of the respondents (45.1%) in this segment were oriented towards news/updates rather than opinions (10.8%). Majority of respondents in this segment (60%) reported maintaining a balance between sharing and learning about what others have shared. 47% of the respondents were in this segment.
3. **Opinion Seekers:** Majority of the respondents (79%) in this segment reported that for them Twitter is about learning about what others have shared. When they tweet, the members of this segment tweet about updates or news rather than opinions.
4. **Voice Makers:** All members of this segment reported that they use Twitter for sharing rather than learning about what others have shared and that when they tweet they tweet about their own opinions. With 12% of the respondents, this segment was the smallest segment.

Figure 37: Twitter Usage Type Segments

Next respondents were asked questions about the types of activities they engaged in when they logged into Twitter (Figure 38). The respondents were asked to indicate how frequently they engaged in these activities using a five-point scale with the values “never”, “less than half of the times I log into Twitter”, “about half of the times I log into Twitter”, “more than half of the times I log into Twitter”, “almost every time I log into Twitter”.

As can also be seen from Figure 38, unsurprisingly, an overwhelming majority of the respondents indicated that they read Tweets from people whose Twitter accounts they follow every time they log into Twitter (88.2%).²¹⁸ In addition, 67% of the users reported reading Tweets from Twitter accounts they do not follow either every time (44.4%) or more than half of the time (22.9%).

²¹⁸ In the context of Twitter, “following” refers to when a Twitter user has added another Twitter user to his/her list and gets instant updates about the Tweets posted by that Twitter user.

Respondents reported writing Tweets much less frequently than reading Tweets. Less than half of respondents (43.5%) reported Tweeting either every time (22.2%) or more than half the time (21.3%). Likewise, only a very small proportion of users indicated that they replied to Tweets more than half the time (8.3%) or every time (6.5%) that they logged into Twitter.

Figure 38: Twitter Activities About Gezi Protests

The high frequency with which our respondents read Tweets from Twitter accounts whom they were not following is in line with data indicating the extensive use of hashtags like #direncezi, #direnaksim, and #occupygezi to follow the protests on Twitter (see Figure 39).

Figure 39: Gezi Protests Hashtag Use (May 30-June 15)²¹⁹

The last set of questions in the survey inquired about the topics (related to Gezi Protests) about which respondents 1) tweeted their opinions (Figure 40), and 2) shared news updates with others through Twitter (Figure 41). For both questions, respondents completed a constant sum scale to indicate what percentage of their Tweets fell into each issue category.

When respondents shared their opinions via Twitter, they most frequently shared their opinions about police interventions (21%), people who were participating in the protests (19%), and reactions of the politicians to the Gezi Protests (18%). Less frequently, respondents also tweeted about their opinions regarding the tone of mass media coverage of the protests (13%) and what they perceived as the reasons of protests (12%).

²¹⁹ Topsy Labs, Inc., <https://pro.topsy.com/#/activity>

Figure 40: On Twitter, when you Tweeted your opinions, they were about...

Likewise, the content that respondents shared via Twitter were most frequently about police interventions (23%), actions of protestors (22%), and the reactions of the politicians to the protests (16%). In addition, in 16% of the tweets within which respondents shared content, the content contained humour about the protests and the police interventions.

Figure 41: On Twitter, when you shared content, they were about...

The fact that opinions and news about police interventions were shared most frequently is in line with the findings summarized in section 6.4, which indicated that for many of the users one of the reasons why they utilized social media was their distrust in mainstream media.

Namely, protestors often voiced concerns that as a result of the lack of sufficient coverage of the protests in mainstream media, key evidence of police abuse was not reaching the public. Hence, social media outlets like Twitter, Facebook, Social Media were the key venues through which evidence of police abuse could be shared.

Cell phone recordings and photos of police violence and misconduct were widely disseminated via social media (figures below).

Figure 42 – A photo depicting how the riot police improperly used the tear gas launcher by directly aiming at the protestors instead of firing the canisters with a 45-degree angle²²⁰

Figure 43 – Photographic and video documentation of police violence on civilians during the protests were frequently disseminated through Twitter, Facebook and Youtube, as well as citizen blogs. Please click on the image on the right to be forwarded to the video footage.

²²⁰ “Police Violence”, *EverywhereTaksim*. 8 June 2013.
<http://everywheretaksim.net/tr/polis-siddeti-3/?nggpage=5>

Also, protestors often disseminated raw footage from CCTV cameras as proof of police misconduct and violence (figure below).

Indeed, in some cases, information shared via social media was key in drawing mass media attention to the events and police misconduct. For example, one protestor used Facebook to describe what he witnessed inside the detention bus when he was detained on June 3, 2013. The Facebook entry was picked up by the mass media when a columnist from *Hürriyet* (one of the largest newspapers in Turkey) shared the entry in his column after being forwarded the entry by a professor from a university in Istanbul.

Figure 44 – This CCTV footage, which was widely disseminated in social media and mainstream media shows policemen hitting three protestors during one of the protests in Antalya. The footage starts with the three protestors escaping into the parking garage and resting by the wall. After entering the garage, the officers spot the protestors, separate them from each other and hit (with batons) and kick the protestors down. The news reports indicate that the footage was obtained by an NGO from the Antalya municipality, which operated the garage.²²¹ As of September 2013, the investigation about this incident, which started after the dissemination of this footage, is going on. Please click on the image on the right to be forwarded to the video footage.

6.6 LESSONS LEARNED

The findings from the online survey underline several important points with regards to the use of social media during political crises such as protests.

²²¹ Tahincioğlu, Gökçer, “3 Gence Otoparkta ‘Kayıtlı’ Dayak”, *Milliyet*, 25 June 2013.
<http://gundem.milliyet.com.tr/3-gence-otoparkta-kayitli-dayak/gundem/detay/1727362/default.htm>

1. Based on the answers they provided to the open ended questions, we can say that respondents were highly pragmatic about the use of social media during the Gezi Protests. In other words, we did not see any comments alluding to the revolutionary potential of social media. Hence, in many respects, the use of social media was driven by a lack of alternatives from mainstream media. Respondents reported that initially they tried to use mainstream media to keep up to date about the events. However, lack of sufficient coverage, particularly in the first day of the protests when the police cracked down the sit in, and biased coverage, led the respondents to seek alternative ways of getting information.
2. In this respect, social media, and particularly Twitter, provided three distinct ways of getting information. First, via the use of hashtags, respondents were able to get information from a loose network of “protestors” and “supporters of protests”. Second, respondents used their close networks to get and share real time updates about specific incidents related to protests across Turkey. Third, personal social media pages (e.g., Twitter pages, blogs) of reputable journalists who worked in established news outlets (which the users did not trust) were followed.
3. Similarly, in terms of sharing information and opinion, social media seemed to have been used to fill the void left by the mainstream media by exposing the alleged cases of police misconduct (and commenting on it) and making visible the protestors and their experience.
4. The analysis revealed that during the protests, there were four distinct types of Twitter users. The most common type, update hubs, comprised users who were not generators of information or opinion leaders. They acted as a clearinghouse of information/opinion in the sense that they focused on searching/receiving information/opinions and then forwarding them to their own networks. Conversely, only a small minority of users, voice makers actively engaged in generating first hand information and opinion for the consumption of others.
5. Users are cognizant that social media may be misused to disseminate misinformation. Still, trust in social media as a source of information, or more precisely trust in information coming from networks of users, is higher than trust in information coming from more established mainstream sources. This is partly the result of the lack of trust in mass media; however, open-ended questions also suggest that users are usually very confident about their ability to filter out misinformation while using social media.

Table 1 summarizes provides a summary of how social media activities during the Gezi Protests map on the six main functions of Social Media during crisis situations as outlined in the COSMIC D2.1 *Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications*:

1. One-way communication (notify/alert)
2. Two-way communication (converse/provide feedback)
3. Request/offer assistance
4. Relay (share a piece of information with others)
5. Campaign (awareness raising/fund raising)
6. Organise (co-ordinate response/enable individuals to organise themselves)²²²

²²² Chapter 2, “State of the art of communication technology for crisis management” of Watson, Hayley, Rachel Finn, Kush Wadhwa and Angelos Yannopoulos, *Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications*, COSMIC D2.1, 31 Aug 2013 also discusses interoperability as a key “need” in crisis management technologies.

Table 1. Functions of Social Media During Gezi Protests

Functions of Social Media (COSMIC D2.1)	Observations from Media Use Data During Istanbul Gezi Protests	Prevalence
One-way communication (notify/alert)	Social media sources quickly replaced mainstream sources for getting information about protests.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 90% percent of users utilized Twitter for reading Tweets from others • Majority of users did not consider themselves as producers of new information
Two-way communication (converse/provide feedback)	Main activities related to this function of social media was voicing opinions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The "Voice Maker" segment who uses Twitter primarily voicing opinions constitute only 12% of the respondents • 44% of the respondents wrote Tweets at least half of the times they logged into Twitter • Only 14% of the respondents replied to Tweets from other people at least half of the times they logged into Twitter
Request/offer assistance	Social media played a role in communication with protestors, and provide assistance and voice support for protestors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 13% of respondents used social media for medical assistance and by providing information about police activities • Another %7 percent indicated that social media was useful for "psychological" support to protestors (comradery)
Relay (share a piece of information with others)	As in other case studies conducted for D2.2., one of the major reasons why Twitter is used during protests is to relay information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The "Update Hubs", who use Twitter for getting and sharing information constitute the largest segment with 47% of the respondents • 60% of respondents Retweeted a Tweet more than half of the times they logged into Twitter
Campaign (awareness raising/fund raising)	Raising awareness about human rights violations and the cause of the protests were among the main reasons why social media was used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 15% of respondents indicated that they relied on social media during the protests because they believed they could raise others' awareness • More than 20% of respondents' Tweets were oriented towards raising public awareness about police misconduct
Organise (co-ordinate response/enable individuals to organise themselves)	Disseminating real time information from protests and coordinating delivery of medical supplies were among the major activities that helped organise protestors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 13% of respondents indicated that they used social media for coordination and organization purposes. • 57% of respondents indicated that up to date information that they needed was only available through social media

7 COLORADO WILDFIRES

In 2012 the State of Colorado was having its worst wildfire season in over a decade, with more than half a dozen forest fires burning across the state's terrain.²²³ The extent of the wildfires was so enormous that they prompted an FBI investigation into the cause of the raging wildfires that displaced thousands of residents and an untold number of homes in Colorado. Local FBI spokesman Dave Joly said that "The FBI Denver Division is working closely with local, state, and federal law enforcement to determine if any of the wild land fires resulted from criminal activity".²²⁴ The wildfires had a great impact in Colorado's society with 32,000 residents in the north western quadrant of Colorado Springs evacuating and 347 homes destroyed in the Waldo Canyon Fire, the largest number in state history.²²⁵ According to a preliminary report, "Colorado fire departments reported 4,167 wild land fires through the National Fire Reporting System. These fires destroyed more than 648 structures, killed six civilians, burned more than 384,803 acres and have caused at least \$538 million in property losses".²²⁶ The Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) was also called upon to provide funds to help fight the fires.²²⁷

Figure 45: Homes burning near the foothills of Colorado Springs on June 26th, 2012.

²²³ Peipert, Thomas, "Colorado Wildfires 2012: Worst Wildfire Season In A Decade; Fires Close In On Tourist Destinations (PHOTOS, VIDEO)", Huffington Post, 26th June 2012. http://www.huffingtonpost.com/2012/06/25/colorado-wildfires-2012-v_n_1623695.html

²²⁴ Fox News, "Raging Wildfires in Colorado prompts FBI investigation", Fox News, 28th June 2012. <http://www.foxnews.com/us/2012/06/28/displaced-colo-residents-wait-as-fire-rages/>

²²⁵ McGhee, Tom, "4,167 Colorado wildfires caused record losses of \$538 million in 2012", The Denver Post, 17th January 2013, http://www.denverpost.com/ci_22396611/4-167-colorado-wildfires-caused-record-losses-538.

²²⁶ Ibid.

²²⁷ Gast, Phil, "32,000 evacuated in fast-moving Colorado Springs wildfire", CNN, 27th June 2012. <http://edition.cnn.com/2012/06/26/us/western-wildfires/index.html>

Data gathered between the 17th and the 24th of June from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MODIS) on NASA's Terra satellite, produced the map of land surface temperature anomalies shown in the figure below. The intensity and scope of the heat wave in the western United States is clearly visible, especially over Colorado, southwest Nebraska and parts of Wyoming.²²⁸

Figure 46: Map of land surface anomalies depicting the intensity of the heat wave in the western United States. (Photo via NASA)

The Colorado wildfires case study is interesting and valuable to the COSMIC project because it occurred only a year ago when all major social media, such as Facebook and Twitter, were already available and established in people's minds as means of communication and information exchange. Therefore, researching social media use during such an event of great magnitude would almost certainly yield important results as to the research purpose of the COSMIC project.

7.1 THE USE OF NEW COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND APPLICATIONS IN THE COLORADO WILDFIRES

During the Colorado fires, several emergency notification systems were in place to provide the possibly affected population with important information, such as the intensity and the

²²⁸ Huff. Post Denver, "Colorado Wildfires 2012: Stunning NASA Map Shows Severe Heat Wave Fueling Wildfires (PHOTO)", Huffington Post, 1st July 2012. http://www.huffingtonpost.com/2012/06/30/waldo-canyon-fire-2012-st_n_1639836.html

direction of the wildfire, location of shelters and evacuation notices. One of these systems though, the Emergency Notification System (ENS) used by the Jefferson County Emergency Communications Authority (JCECA) failed to work properly during the fire.²²⁹ These ENS systems rely on a relationship between a phone number and the physical location associated with that number. If a phone number is registered to receive warnings about possible disasters in the area, then, when such cases arise this phone number will receive an automated call providing information about the situation. In the case of the Lower North Fork Fire, which occurred in Jefferson County, a significant number of evacuation notifications were either sent to addresses that were nowhere near the wildfire or were not sent at all to those addresses that were immediately affected by the fire and were located inside the evacuation zone (Figure 47). Post event examinations showed more than 100,000 mappings between phone numbers and their physical locations in the system's database. At least one death was directly attributed to this failure.²³⁰ Similar warning systems are placed in other Colorado counties but all of them were able to properly warn and inform citizens of any actions they should take to prepare or deal with the fire.

Figure 47: Map depicting the mislabelled homes which should have received an emergency notification but did not.

During the 2012 Colorado wildfires, the Google Crisis Response team issued a crisis map where all major fires of Colorado were depicted. All media were reporting on the massive wildfires of Colorado, and Google's map was an effort to provide related information to those

²²⁹ EPC Updates, "Colorado Wildfire: Emergency Notification System Failure", [epcupdates.com](http://www.epcupdates.com), 20th April 2012. <http://www.epcupdates.org/2012/04/colorado-wildfire-emergency.html>

²³⁰ Ibid.

affected. The map featured fire perimeters cropped from the U.S. Geological Survey, Red Cross, and satellite imagery by DigitalGlobe.²³¹ The Google map is shown in Figure 48.

The Colorado Division of Fire Prevention & Control also provided information on the wildfires by its Android application. Using this application the Colorado citizens could stay informed on wildfires and relief efforts across the state of Colorado with the “Colorado Wildfire Watch” application, shown in Figure 49. The purpose of the application was to alert the population of any actions they should perform but also to avoid confusion and misinformation. What the application provides can be summarized in the following:²³²

- A list of all active fires across Colorado along with descriptions, evacuation and contact information.

Figure 48: Google map issued by the Google Crisis Response team.

²³¹ ÉLYSE B, "Google Crisis Response team launches new crisis map for raging US wildfires", 9to5google.com, 29th June 2012. <http://9to5google.com/2012/06/29/google-crisis-response-team-launches-new-crisis-map-for-raging-u-s-wildfires/>

²³² Google, https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.app_cowildfires.layout

Figure 49: Android “Colorado Wildfire Watch” application

- A map with all active fires and evacuation centres plotted on it. The user can also tap a location on the map and get details and directions for each location.
- Updates on all active fires.
- The application can also be used as social media by providing Twitter feeds for most fires and allowing users to stay informed by reading tweets posted by the agency.

7.2 THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE COLORADO WILDFIRES

The use of social media by authorities and the public focused on established applications such as websites, Twitter and Facebook. Authorities primarily used social media for one-way communication from authorities to members of the public as well as for soliciting information from the public. The public on the other hand used social media for one-way communication, for relaying information and for campaigning.

Colorado Office of Emergency Management within the Division of Homeland Security and Emergency Management used Facebook to inform the public of ongoing operations on their Twitter²³³ and Facebook pages,²³⁴ as shown in Figure 50. This included specifically the use of social media to gather and share information, to post alerts, and possibly receive information about potentially new fire outbreaks. When the disaster struck, several hashtags were also created so that Twitter users could comment on each fire separately. Hashtags were

²³³ Colorado Office of Emergency Management, <https://twitter.com/COEmergency/media/grid>

²³⁴ Colorado Office of Emergency Management, <https://www.facebook.com/COEmergency>

disseminated throughout traditional media, such as television (Figure 51) so as to make sure that it reached as many people as possible. The initial hashtags in use for Colorado wildfires were the following:

- #HighParkFire — The High Park fire near Fort Collins
- #WaldoCanyonFire — The Waldo Canyon fire in Colorado Springs
- #FlagstaffFire — The Flagstaff fire burning in Boulder
- #LittleSandFire — The Little Sand fire near Pagosa Springs
- #TreasureFire — The Treasure fire is near Leadville
- #StateLineFire — The State Line fire is burning south of Durango
- #SpringerFire — The Springer fire near Lake George (contained)
- #LastChanceFire — The Last Chance fire burned 45,000 acres in 8 hours
- #COfire — Catchall for Colorado wildfire information
- #Wildfire — Catchall for any wildfire information

On the 6th of September 2010, several new hashtags were created when fire broke out in Four Mile Canyon west of Boulder. #FourmileFire, #4mileFire, #FourmileCanyonFire and #BoulderFire were all used initially, sometimes all at once.²³⁵

²³⁵ Schneider, Daniel J, "What's in a #name? Hashtags and Colorado wildfires", The Denver Post, 26th June 2012. <http://blogs.denverpost.com/techknowbytes/2012/06/26/hashtags-colorado-wildfires/5156/>

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Figure 50: Colorado Office of Emergency Management Facebook page.

Figure 51: TV broadcast informing the public of the #waldocanyonfire hashtag.

Members of the public also used social media in various ways during the crisis. For example, several businesses used social media during the fires to inform their clients of current conditions concerning themselves and the situation in general.²³⁶

In the example provided in Figure 52(a), the Flying W Ranch let their followers know that they had to evacuate, but save what they could. Later, they posted that the phones were down, but they could still be reached through their Facebook page. In another case, shown in Figure 52(b), **Chefs Catalog** alerted people to what was happening and kept them in the loop. Their phones were down and they let customers know so they wouldn't worry or wonder what is happening. **Chefs Catalog** used Facebook for its communication with the public and received some great responses and encouragement from their customers:²³⁷

Figure 52: Members of the public and specifically local businesses used social media to inform their customers.

An important use of social media during the crisis was also to share and relay important third-party information between organizations and citizens. Re-sharing and re-tweeting information will most likely reach family, friends, customers or community and can provide help quickly to someone who may needs it. An example of such a case is shown in Figure 53, where a news organisation in Colorado Springs shared everything they could, newsworthy or

²³⁶ Bastian, Jill, "How Colorado Businesses Used Social Media During the Fires", Vertical Response Marketing Blog, 9th July 2012. <http://www.verticalresponse.com/blog/how-colorado-businesses-used-social-media-during-the-fires/>

²³⁷ Ibid.

otherwise on social media including: recent evacuations, upcoming press conferences, places taking in evacuees, even what the firefighters needed donated. They strongly urged the people reading their posts to share their status in order for them to reach as many people as possible.

Figure 53: KKTV urged people to re-share their posts to reach as many people as possible.

Researchers at the University of Colorado at Colorado Springs and the University of California at Irvin participated in a project titled “Project Heroic” (funded by the National Science Foundation). The objective of the project was to “to better understand the dynamics of informal online communication in response to extreme events.” As part of this project, the team turned their attention to analysing Tweets surrounding the recent Waldo Canyon Fire, which started on the 23rd of 2012.²³⁸

The data collected for this study, which focused on the online response of the public during the Waldo Canyon Fire, included public tweets from Twitter containing the #waldocanyonfire hashtag posted between June 25th, 2012 and July 10th, 2012. Over 100,000 messages from more than 25,000 unique Twitter users were collected in this initial period of collection. This data allowed researchers to estimate an hourly usage rate of the hashtag #waldocanyonfire for this period.

The time series of the posting rate is shown in Figure 54. Night and day panels are distinguished by the background colour (gray covers the hours of 8:00 pm MDT to 8:00 am MDT). Hourly variations are clearly visible as the rate of posting drops drastically during night hours. Peak activity occurs around 9:00 pm MDT on June 26th, 2012 — coinciding with the time the fire moved towards residential areas.²³⁹ We can see from the figure that peak activity reached almost 7,000 tweets per hour during those crucial moments.

²³⁸ Stephens, Kim, "Researchers Study Waldo Canyon Fire Twitter Activity", idisaster 2.0-Social Media and Emergency Management, 4th September 2012. <http://idisaster.wordpress.com/2012/09/04/researchers-study-waldo-canyon-fire-twitter-activity/>

²³⁹ Spiro, E., Sutton, J., Johnson, B., Fitzhugh, S., and Butts, C. (2012). “HEROIC Team Explores Waldo Canyon Wildfire in Colorado.” Online Research Highlight. <http://heroicproject.org>

Figure 54: Tweets per hour during the wildfires.

In addition to collecting public tweets, research also focused on a set of regional and local official government entities involved in the response. A total of 16 accounts were initially identified as key players in communicating official information to members of the general public. One of the questions that the study focused on was the effect of the Waldo Canyon Fire on the numbers of individuals following these government accounts. In Figure 55, for each of the government accounts, the percentage increase in follower count and number of accounts being followed during the time period of interest are shown.

As shown, many of the accounts, and particularly the accounts of local organizations, gain large numbers of followers during the initial onset of the fire. However, none of the government accounts seems to add many new following relationships over the observation period, as seen in the right panel below. Government accounts tend not to change their online relationships during the wildfire, while general public users actively seek information from official accounts by following them.²⁴⁰

²⁴⁰ Ibid.

A retweet allows a user to re-post information they have been exposed to so that each of their followers also has the opportunity to see the original message. In Figure 57, the probability that any given message posted by one of the government accounts is retweeted at least once is calculated and a comparison of the chance of being retweeted before and during the wildfire for each organization is shown.²⁴²

Figure 57: Probability of a tweet being retweeted before and during the crisis.

The organizations to the right of the figure represent organizations local to Colorado Springs. Though most organizations see their retweet probability increase during the wildfire, this increase is largest for such local organizations. Government accounts on the other hand have a high chance of being retweeted even before the wildfire. The FEMA for example will have its tweets retweeted at least once by another user, having a retweet probability of almost 1.²⁴³

7.3 LESSONS LEARNED

Based on their findings, the researchers at the University of Colorado at Colorado Springs and the University of California at Irvin drew some conclusions:²⁴⁴

- A large number of people will follow local organizations on their Twitter account during a crisis.
- Organizations should not pay attention to low interest in their social media accounts during the absence of crises. Establishing a social media strategy before a crisis occurs is important.
- Content generation on Twitter varies predictably during a day. Organizations should therefore interpret changes in attention accordingly.

²⁴² Ibid.

²⁴³ Ibid.

²⁴⁴ Stephens, Kim, "Researchers Study Waldo Canyon Fire Twitter Activity", *idisaster 2.0-Social Media and Emergency Management*, 4th September 2012. <http://idisaster.wordpress.com/2012/09/04/researchers-study-waldo-canyon-fire-twitter-activity/>

- Original content tends to be produced by local organizations as they are the ones who are at the front dealing with the crisis. Non-locals tend to relay information.
- Twitter will most likely be used as a broadcast channel rather than a conversational channel.
- Hashtag use indicates that these organizations are becoming more sophisticated regarding how to participate effectively during a disaster event.

Apart from the lessons learned that were drawn from the research study on Twitter use during the wildfire, we can also conclude the following:

- It is highly unlikely that major organisations' Facebook and Twitter pages will be offline during a crisis. Social media can act as counterweight when conventional warning systems fail to operate, like the case was with the Emergency Notification System (ENS) used by the Jefferson County Emergency Communications Authority. Therefore, authorities should not neglect to update their social media pages regularly.
- Social media users should not just visit online pages just to inform themselves about the current situation but instead be involved as much as possible in the dissemination of the information by re-sharing and retweeting potentially valuable information to people in need.

7.4 CONCLUSION

The Colorado wildfires was an excellent case study for researching the use of social media. Due to the large scale crisis, which affected a large number of the population and the familiarity of both the public and the authorities with social media, we were able to come to useful conclusions as to whether social media were used wisely and how they could perform even better in educating the public about preparedness, informing them of potential crises and saving their lives by asking them to provide feedback on the situation in their own neighbourhood.

8 U.K. FLOODS

During the biggest part of 2012, the United Kingdom was severely hit by a series of weather events that had great impact on its population. At the beginning of 2012 the country experienced droughts and a heatwave, which were then followed by massive floods throughout the country for the remainder of the year as well as the start of 2013. 2012 saw record breaking amounts of rainfall while the months of April and June were both individually the wettest since records began in 1910, with the period from April through June also seeing unprecedented accumulations of rainfall for the UK. The result has been numerous flood events across England and Wales.²⁴⁵

The main reason for such a prolonged period of heavy rainfall was the positioning of the jet stream, which passed to the south of the UK over France and Spain rather than following a more eastward direction, as Figure 58 indicates.²⁴⁶

Figure 58: Jet stream's positions.

Almost 8,000 homes and businesses were flooded in 2012, as the UK was battered by repeated heavy rain, storms and floods. Through the year, nearly 200,000 homes received a flood warning from the Environment Agency's free flood warning service, and the agency

²⁴⁵ JBA Risk Management Limited and Met Office Report, "UK Flooding April to July 2012", 2012. http://www.metoffice.gov.uk/media/pdf/e/s/JBA_and_Met_Office_Bulletin_UK_Flooding_April_July_2012.pdf

²⁴⁶ Ibid.

said 199,632 homes were protected from floods by defences.²⁴⁷ In 2012 it's estimated that £600 million worth of crops such as potatoes and wheat was lost. The apple crop was affected and honey production dropped by around 75%. The timing of the severe weather also played an important part to this disaster.²⁴⁸

Figure 59: Aerial view of the area around Bracklesham in West Sussex.²⁴⁹

Partners have selected the UK floods case study because of its widespread effect on the population and because it occurred recently enough for social media to have played an important role in every aspect of the disaster as it unfolded. As such, the case presented the partners with an excellent opportunity to study social media use in a country where most organizations have their own social media pages readily available in case a crisis struck.

²⁴⁷ The Huffington Post, "Thousands Hit By 2012 Floods With Wettest Summer For A Century", The Huffington Post, 31st December 2012. http://www.huffingtonpost.co.uk/2012/12/31/thousands-hit-by-2012-floods_n_2388664.html

²⁴⁸ MET Office Education, "November 2012 flooding - Met Office Education", MET Office, 2012. <http://www.metoffice.gov.uk/education/teens/case-studies/november-2012-flooding>

²⁴⁹ The Telegraph, "Weather: parts of Britain under water as torrential rain causes flash floods", The Telegraph, 2012. <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/topics/weather/9326993/Weather-parts-of-Britain-under-water-as-torrential-rain-causes-flash-floods.html?frame=2246259>

8.1 THE USE OF NEW COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND APPLICATIONS IN THE U.K. FLOODS

The Environment Agency issued a message stating that “residents are urged to find out whether they are at risk of flooding by calling Floodline on 0845 988 1188 or by visiting our website at www.environment-agency.gov.uk/flood. Eligible residents will be able to sign up to Floodline Warnings Direct which is a free service that sends you a direct message when flooding is expected and may affect your property. You can receive warnings by telephone, mobile, email, SMS text message or fax.”²⁵⁰ Warnings, such as the ones shown in Figure 60 were published in major mass media outlets and in social media.

Figure 60: Floodline Warnings Direct warnings.

²⁵⁰ Hebden Bridge Times, "More flood help offered", Hebden Bridge Times, 18th July 2012. <http://www.hebdenbridgetimes.co.uk/news/local/more-flood-help-offered-1-4751357>

Whenever bad weather was imminent, the MET office would issue forecasts and warnings via traditional

media, such as television and their website (Figure 61).
 Figure 61: Weather forecast issued by the MET office, which was broadcasted in all traditional media channels.

).²⁵¹ The Environment Agency would also act similarly by posting warnings on their website, as shown in Figure

Status	Yorks	Midland	Northwest	Northwest	Southeast	Southeast	Wales	Totals
Severe Flood Warning Severe flooding. Danger to life.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
Flood Warning Flooding is expected. Immediate action required.	24	68	38	1	22	16	3	172
Flood Risk Flooding is possible. Be prepared.	32	44	26	4	43	22	13	184
Warning no longer in force Flood warnings and flood alerts that have been removed in the last 24 hours.	15	36	27	11	23	56	13	181

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Figure 62: Warnings posted on the Environment Agency’s webpage.

. The webpage displays the number of flood warnings in force by region. There are four levels of warnings. The lowest level is the one where no warning is in force. The next level is a flood alert, where flooding is possible and people are advised to prepare for a flood. The third

²⁵¹ Allen, Emily, "UK weather: Block of flats in Newburn evacuated after floods wash away its foundations | Mail Online", Mail Online, 25th September 2012. <http://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-2208269/UK-weather-Block-flats-Newburn-evacuated-floods-wash-away-foundations.html>

level is a flood warning, where flooding is expected and immediate action is required. Finally, the highest level is that of a severe flooding warning, where severe flooding has occurred and there is a high danger to life.

Figure 61: Weather forecast issued by the MET office, which was broadcasted in all traditional media channels.

Status	London	Midlands	Northwest	North East	Southeast	South West	Other	Total
Severe Flood Warning Severe flooding. Danger to life.	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
Flood Warning Flooding is expected. Immediate action required.	24	68	38	1	22	16	3	172
Flood Alert Flooding is possible. Be prepared.	32	44	26	4	43	22	13	184
Warning no longer in force Flood warnings and flood alerts that have been removed in the last 24 hours	15	36	27	11	23	56	13	181

Figure 62²⁵²: Warnings posted on the Environment Agency’s webpage.

8.2 THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE U.K. FLOODS

²⁵² Environment Agency, <http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/homeandleisure/floods/31618.aspx>

The use of social media by authorities and the public focused on established applications such as websites, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube and Flickr. The Authorities primarily used social media for one-way (from authorities to members of public) and two-way communication. The public, on the other hand, used social media mostly as a way of staying informed of all developments and news about the flooding and to a lesser extent to relay information posted on social webpages maintained by local authorities and other stakeholders. In most of the social media webpages, people would only comment on the information provided by the stakeholders and very few would consider re-sharing their content to their own friends or followers.

One example of how social media was used by authorities for one-way communication was Flood Alerts, which is a free to use application provided by the Environment Agency and developed by Shoot Hill to provide users in England and Wales with flood warnings:

"FloodAlerts is the first graphical representation of the flood warning data which provides localised updates every 15 minutes, keeping users informed about the potential flood risks in their area. To monitor a location you will need to register with the Flood alerts app on Facebook. When we issue a flood alert that affects your monitored location; you will receive a notification on Facebook and your registered Facebook email address. This alert will send you a direct link to the relevant flood warning(s) on the map, shown in Figure

63

Figure 63: Flood alerts issued by the Environment Agency.

, giving you a chance to assess the situation as it develops."²⁵³

Flood alerts were also used in Twitter to warn people about flooding (Figure 64).

²⁵³ Mapperz Blogspot, "Mapping News by Mapperz", Mapperz - The Mapping News Blog, 18th July 2012. http://mapperz.blogspot.gr/2012_07_01_archive.html

Figure 63: Flood alerts issued by the Environment Agency.

Figure 64: Environment Agency's FloodAlerts Twitter page.

The Environment Agency also has its own Facebook, Twitter and Flickr accounts, as shown in the figures below, which were used to communicate with the public. Social media were

used during the incident by the Environment Agency, both to monitor conversations and to warn and inform the public about the situation. Social media, primarily Twitter, were monitored proactively between 8am and 10pm, and at other times by the out of hour's duty press officer. The common characteristic identified in all of the above social accounts though is that, considering the vast impact that flooding had on several areas of the U.K., only a few people were aware of the need to re-share content provided by the authorities to their own friends and followers.

Figure 65: The Environment Agency posted photos of the flooding and the rescue operations on Flickr.

Figure 66: The Environment Agency posted warnings on their Facebook account's timeline.

Figure 67: Environment Agency tweeted information and advice about the floods.

The Agency also has a YouTube channel, shown below, where internet users can stay up-to-date with all the latest developments, receive valuable advice and share their concerns and thoughts with other users in the comments section. However, there is only a small number of users registered to this channel, which probably suggests that either the channel is not well known to the public or people will try to stay informed of possible flooding through other channels.

Figure 68: Environment Agency’s YouTube channel. News of the flooding and advice to the civilians were given by special broadcasts.

The Agency posted photos of their Operations Teams to demonstrate what they were doing on the ground.²⁵⁴ During the incident, the regional Twitter account, @EnvAgencySE was contacted by members of the public with questions regarding flooding and informing the Agency where flooding had occurred.²⁵⁵

The highlights of November and December were the following with regards to the Agency’s actions:

- The Agency issued 244 tweets in November about the flooding situation and 180 tweets in December.

²⁵⁴ Environment Agency, “Flood Event Report Winter 2012/13 West Thames Area. U.K”, Environment Agency, February 2013. http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/static/documents/Research/Winter_2012-13_WT_Area_Flood_Event_Report.pdf

²⁵⁵ Ibid.

- Number of followers to the @EnvAgencySE increased by 30% in November and by 20.5% in December.
- The Agency was retweeted 653 times by local authorities, media, key partners and members of the public in November and 1,222 times in December.
- The Agency was mentioned 156 times on Twitter in November. A tweet from Thames Valley Police on the 22 November telling people to visit our website to keep up to date with the latest information went to 18,840 of their followers. In December the Agency was mentioned 249 times on Twitter, including a mention from one of the MPs.
- The Agency’s official tweeters sent out 111 messages in November and 58 times in December about their jobs on the ground helping to deal with the incident.
- The Agency’s website was accessed more than 2,100 times from the South East Twitter account in December.

Other organisations created Facebook pages to offer help to people in need. An example organisation is the “Flood Action 4 Buckingham” shown in the next figure. They provided information specifically about the floods in the area of Buckingham.²⁵⁶ They also kept their friends and followers up-to-date with their actions in mitigating the impacts of the floods. They also tried to organise the public by recruiting volunteers. The number of re-shares was extremely low though, which means that people would visit the website to learn about possible developments about the flooding but would not think about re-sharing the content to help spread the news to people who may find it helpful.

²⁵⁶ <https://www.facebook.com/FloodAction4Buckingham>

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Figure 69: The Flood Action 4 Buckingham Facebook page.

The National Flood Forum is a national charity dedicated to supporting and representing communities and individuals at risk of flooding. Their goal is to help people prepare for flooding to mitigate its impacts as well as help them recover in case they have been flooded. The Forum were using their Facebook and Twitter accounts to inform the citizens of the current state of the floods.²⁵⁷

²⁵⁷ National Flood Forum, <http://www.floodforum.org.uk/>

Figure 70: National Flood Forum’s Facebook and Twitter page.

Researchers from the Guardian have studied the digital trails of the UK floods to try to answer the question of whether tweets match observations of flooding.²⁵⁸ Concentration of twitter activity (in this case tweets containing the keyword *flood*) seem to closely reflect the actual locations of floods and flood alerts. This can be observed in Figure 71, where the map on the left, issued by the MET office, depicts the rainfall levels between the 20th and 27th of November and the map on the right depicts a tweets map for the corresponding dates. Values greater than one indicate that more tweets were posted than would be expected in normal Twitter traffic.

Figure 71: (a) The Met Office map of UK rainfall between 20 and 27 November, (b) a normalized Tweets map.

8.3 LESSONS LEARNED

The main lesson learned in this case study is that since floods affect the general population, meaning that there is no direct social group that is affected the most, it would be wise for organizations and authorities to utilize both traditional media technologies and social media when supporting and communicating with the public. The Guardian’s research supports this.

The underlying conclusion of the study is that people will put Twitter, in this specific case, into good use even during a crisis, to potentially express their concerns and thoughts, try to stay up-to-date with the latest developments and provide feedback to local authorities and other stakeholders.

²⁵⁸ Graham, Mark, "Digital trails of the UK floods - how well do tweets match observations? | News | theguardian.com", The Guardian, 28th November 2012, <http://www.theguardian.com/news/datablog/2012/nov/28/data-shadows-twitter-uk-floods-mapped>

The problem that partners identified in this particular case study is that even though members of the public would actively use social media for all the reasons mentioned above, they would rarely consider the need to re-share important information found with on authorities' and other stakeholders' social webpages with their own friends and followers. This would lead to information not reaching people who may actually have found it helpful.

All stakeholders involved in such a crisis should therefore inform the population that information posted on their social media webpages should always be re-shared so as to reach as many people as possible.

8.4 CONCLUSION

The case study of UK floods is a perfect example of how social media can be used in time of crisis. All social media received widespread attention and involvement by the public during the UK floods of 2012. The two main organizations that played an important role in informing the general population about imminent floods, namely the MET office and the Environment Agency, used a variety of social media tools to accomplish their purpose. They both engaged in issuing warnings and alerts on their website and their social media pages, such as Facebook, Twitter YouTube and Flickr, posted updates on rescue operations and gave advice to the affected population about how to cope with the effects of the flooding. Social media use in this case study supplemented the use of traditional media and offered an alternative way of communication between the authorities and the public.

9 XYNTHIA STORM

In 2010, between the 27th of February and the 1st of March, a violent storm, named Xynthia, crossed Western Europe, with Portugal, Spain, France, Germany and Belgium all suffering strong gusts and heavy rain.²⁵⁹ France, the worst-hit country, recorded at least 51 victims and several missing, mainly in Vendee and Charente-Maritime, the two western coastal provinces, which registered the biggest toll. Most victims died from drowning or from falling trees and buildings.²⁶⁰ Direct losses amounted to more than 2.5 billion Euros.²⁶¹ Catastrophe risk modelling firm AIR Worldwide has estimated that insured losses in France, Belgium, Germany, and Netherlands from the storm to be between €1.5 billion and €3 billion.²⁶² Other estimations by Deutsche Rückversicherung AG calculated insurance costs of around 2 billion Euros in France alone.²⁶³

Figure 72: Map depicting the direction of Xynthia storm. The provinces of Vendee and Charente-Maritime were affected the most.

²⁵⁹Mu Xuequan, "Violent winter storm kills 62 in western Europe", Xinhua News, 3rd March 2010. http://news.xinhuanet.com/english2010/world/2010-03/03/c_13194575.htm

²⁶⁰Ibid.

²⁶¹GENOVESE, Elisabetta, Valentin PRZYLUSKI, and Stéphane HALLEGATTE, "Disaster Risk Management and Territorial Governance: Lessons from Xynthia Storm in France", International Federation of Surveyors, France, 2012. http://www.fig.net/pub/fig2012/papers/ts09f/TS09F_genovese_przyluski_et_al_6048.pdf

²⁶²Claims Journal, "AIR Estimates Windstorm Xynthia Insured Losses at \$2 to \$4.1 Billion", AIR Worldwide, 3rd March 2010. <http://www.claimsjournal.com/news/international/2010/03/03/107818.htm>

²⁶³German Weather Service, "Severe Storm Xynthia over southwestern and western Europe. Germany", Federal Ministry of Transport, Building and Urban Development, 2010. http://www.environmental-auditing.org/Portals/0/AuditFiles/France_s_eng_Lessons-from-2010-Floods.pdf

Xynthia affected French society in various ways. Houses, agricultural fields, and shellfish companies were severely flooded with seawater leading to the loss of crops and major damages inside people's homes. Due to their homes being damaged by the floods, several thousand people temporarily had to leave their homes, an action which had an impact on their psychology as an increase in psychotropic drug deliveries was noticed after the Xynthia storm.²⁶⁴ Because of the storm, power was cut off to more than 1 million homes in France, and up to 1 million customers in Portugal.^{265, 266} Transportation was also severely hit with rail services in northern Spain unable to function properly. In addition, a number of trains in western France were delayed due to flooded tracks. Air France said 100 of its flights had been cancelled from Charles de Gaulle airport in Paris.²⁶⁷

Figure 73: La-Faute-sur-Mer, western France, March 2, 2010 after Xynthia. A rescue crew in a SAR operation.

The case study of Xynthia super storm is of interest to the COSMIC project as it presents us with the opportunity to study how people reacted to the catastrophic floods. As will be discussed in this chapter, there was very little evidence of social media use prior to and during the crisis. This may be linked to the short period of time in which the storm spread across France before moving forward to Germany. As the storm occurred in the evening, the full extent of the damage was not fully recognised until the next day.

²⁶⁴ Motreff, Yvon, Philippe Pirard, and Sarah Goria, "Increase in Psychotropic Drug Deliveries after the Xynthia Storm, France, 2010", *Prehospital and disaster medicine*, Vol. 28, 2013, pp. 1-5. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S1049023X13008662>

²⁶⁵ Masters, Jeff, "Dr. Jeff Masters' WunderBlog : Winter Storm Xynthia kills 62 in Europe | Weather Underground", Weather Undergroud, 1st March 2010. <http://www.wunderground.com/blog/JeffMasters/winter-storm-xynthia-kills-62-in-europe>

²⁶⁶ BBC, "BBC News - At least 50 dead in western Europe storms", BBC News, 28th February 2010. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/europe/8540762.stm>

²⁶⁷ Ibid.

9.1 THE USE OF NEW COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND APPLICATIONS DURING STORM XYNTHIA

It is certainly the case that just before storm Xynthia hit France, authorities relied upon traditional and new communication technologies (e.g., television, radio and websites) to inform the public of the imminent danger rather than social media. France's flood response plan mainly revolves around alerts provided by two services, namely Meteo France and the "Service Central d'Hydrométéorologie et d'Appui à la Prévision des Inondations" (SCHAPI). Both will be further discussed below.

As shown in Figure 74, Meteo France issued a warning on its website on the 27th of February, stating that a severe storm was imminent. However, missing in this warning was the potential for the storm to cause flooding. Specifically, Meteo France had clearly provided a warning for the storm on all the TV networks and also given storm surge warnings, but the weather maps of Meteo France that were shown on TV provided no information on the-risk of flooding. A symbol was used to indicate strong winds but there was no corresponding notification for the high probability of flooding. The reason for this lack of a flooding warning was that even though Météo France correctly managed to forecast rising water levels, they underestimated the extent of this phenomenon in areas such as the La Rochelle, with forecasts putting the flood surge at between 0.80 metres and 1 metre, compared with an actual high water line of 1.5metres. There were known deficiencies in the forecasting system, such as a lack of automated tide gauges and observation stations belonging to the Naval Hydro - graphical and Oceanographic Department (SHOM) around the edge of the bay of Bourgneuf and the cove of L'Aiguillon-sur-Mer. These shortcomings, which affected virtually all coastal areas subject to a high risk of significant flooding, are regrettable, even if correcting them would only have had an impact if substantial progress had also been made on coastal oceanographic models.²⁶⁸

Therefore, since the residents of the flooded areas did not receive a flood warning they would probably have not been able to prepare for the floods, and in fact most likely considered themselves safe from the storm and had taken little or none measures of precaution in case their homes were to flood. As the population prepared for high winds and not for flooding this was fatal for some. Whilst some individuals took measures such as closing windows and (electric) shutters, others were restricted in their defence capabilities during the storm, as those areas affected by a blackout or flowing may have lacked the power to operate their shutters.

That fact that the civil servants did not understand the nature of the flood is illustrated by the interview with Mrs. Beatrice Lagarde, a high ranking official (sous préfet of the Vendée) after

²⁶⁸ Cour des Comptes - Summary of the Public Thematic Report, "Lessons from the 2010 floods on the Atlantic coast (Xynthia) and in the Var", France, 2012. http://www.environmental-auditing.org/Portals/0/AuditFiles/France_s_eng_Lessons-from-2010-Floods.pdf

the flood. She spoke of the impossibility to evacuate 400,000 people on account of the storm when evacuating a few thousand people would have saved about thirty lives.²⁶⁹

In France the “Service Central d’Hydrométéorologie et d’Appui à la Prévision des Inondations” (SCHAPI), part of the Ministry of Ecology, Sustainable Development and Planning, was established after the floods of 2003. Real time river water levels are monitored by approximately 1500 measuring stations. Data is used, among others, for a daily update of the so-called flood alerting map, shown in Figure 75. This alerting map distinguishes between four threat levels, varying from green (no special alertness) to red (risk of major floods). At the time when Xynthia hit France, and indeed until present time, the system does not seem to be focused on coastal floods which led to the public’s inability of staying informed about possible flooding because of the storm.²⁷⁰

Figure 74: Below is the “carte de vigilance” for the 27th of February 2010, put out by Météo France on its website.

²⁶⁹ Kolen, Bas, Robert Slomp, Wim van Balen, Teun Terpstra, Marcel Bottema, and Stefan Nieuwenhuis, “Learning from French experiences with storm Xynthia. Netherlands: Ministerie van Verkeer en Waterstaat”, 2010. <http://www.scribd.com/doc/85996822/Learning-from-French-experiences-with-storm-Xynthia-damages-after-a-flood>

²⁷⁰ Kolen, Bas, Robert Slomp, Wim van Balen, Teun Terpstra, Marcel Bottema, and Stefan Nieuwenhuis, “Learning from French experiences with storm Xynthia. Netherlands: Ministerie van Verkeer en Waterstaat”, 2010. http://www.environmental-auditing.org/Portals/0/AuditFiles/France_s_eng_Lessons-from-2010-Floods.pdf

Figure 75²⁷¹: Flood warning system.

As previously discussed, the public in general and civilians living in the affected areas were able to stay up-to-date with what had happened mostly through traditional media channels. Television and radio broadcasts as well as news websites were reporting news from the flooded areas and statements made by officials in support of the victims of the storm, such as Nicolas Sarkozy's announcement of a series of measures, including the release of 3 million euros to assist victims (Figure 76). The decree recognizing the state of natural disaster was also published in the Official Journal of 2nd of March.²⁷²

²⁷¹ The Ministry of Ecology, Sustainable Development and Energy, 2013. <http://www.vigicrues.ecologie.gouv.fr/>

²⁷² Premier Ministre, Portail du Gouvernement, "Tempête Xynthia : Nicolas Sarkozy a annoncé le déblocage de 3 millions d'euros", Archives François Fillon 2009/2012, 2nd March 2010. http://archives.gouvernement.fr/fillon_version2/gouvernement/tempete-xynthia-nicolas-sarkozy-a-annonce-le-deblocage-de-3-millions-d-euros.html

Figure 76²⁷³: TV channels and online news agencies showed official statements about the victims of Xynthia.

9.2 THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE XYNTHIA STORM

The use of social media by authorities and members of the public during the storm was predominantly focused on established applications such as Twitter and Facebook. According to partners' research, the authorities used social media neither before nor after the disaster as they relied on traditional means, such as the television and news websites to relay their information to the public. Our research has not indicated any reasons as to why this was the case. The storm was initially thought to bring strong winds to France's Atlantic coast line but it was only until the early hours of the 28th of February when it became clear that flooding had also occurred. There was therefore no time for social media to be used either before or during the storm. The next few days, response teams were mobilized to aid the victims but there is little documented evidence to suggest that social media were used to contribute to these operations. Also, according to our research, local authorities did not, at the time, have any social media accounts and were therefore unable to communicate with the local population via that particular method.

On the other hand, evidence suggests that some members of the public primarily used social media to share information among them, exchange thoughts on the disaster but also to campaign in order to find funds to support the victims of the storm. News agencies also used social media to inform the public of the impacts of the storm and how the recovery process progressed even several months after the event had occurred.

²⁷³ Le Telegram, "Sarkozy annonce des mesures pour les victimes de Xynthia", 1st March 2010. <http://videos.letelegramme.fr/player.php?sig=iLyROafvgvy&overlay=1&rub=0>

From all social media present at the time, Facebook was the most actively used for the purposes of exchanging information between the public and campaigning for support to the Xynthia victims. Several such cases are presented in the following three figures.

As seen in the figure below, a Facebook page was created on the 28th of February to offer support to the victims of Xynthia. The page's purpose was to inform the public of support actions that were carried out and involve them in the process. The page received widespread acceptance with more than 33,000 likes.

Figure 77: Facebook page campaigning for support of the victims of Xynthia.

After the storm had hit France, the French government decided to mark parts of the flooded areas as black zones, where all houses would be demolished. France's Prime Minister, François Fillon, said that "The state and the local authorities do not have the right to risk letting people return to areas where they could be in mortal danger". Many residents accused the government of over-reaction and claimed that black zones were drawn arbitrarily.²⁷⁴ Several pages were created on Facebook to campaign against the demolition of the houses, as seen in the figure below. The page shared news about the government's plan to demolish all houses inside the black zones and urged people to react to such plans. Most of the discussions concerned the black zones and whether their homes were actually inside them.

²⁷⁴ Alexander, Harriet, "French villagers hit by floods fight demolition of hundreds of 'black zone' homes", The Telegraph, 17th April 2010. <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/europe/france/7601384/French-villagers-hit-by-floods-fight-demolition-of-hundreds-of-black-zone-homes.html>

Figure 78: Facebook page campaigning against the destruction of the homes affected by Xynthia storm.

Several Facebook groups about Xynthia storm were also created where users could exchange thoughts and news about the crises, offer support and again campaign against the demolition of houses inside designated black areas. The figure below depicts such groups, for example a group which offers support to the residents of the Oleron Island and a group which tries to raise awareness on the government’s plans of demolishing homes in Boyard.

Figure 79: Facebook page and related groups concerning Xynthia storm.

Some organizations, such as the Saur Group, also used Facebook to inform the public of activities performed on their part to restore previous living conditions to the affected areas. The Saur group is a group of companies that support local authorities and industry in their

projects related to water, waste management, engineering, jobs and recreation. Their priority was to restore drinking water to all households and provide human, material and logistical support to communities according to their needs. Their progress was communicated to the public via status updates on their Facebook page, which is shown below.²⁷⁵

Figure 80: Saur Group Facebook statuses informing the public of their effort to support the victims of Xynthia.

Twitter was also used in some cases, where hashtags were created by the public, namely #xynthia and #tempete (French for “storm”), to allow users to interact on this specific topic. Tweeting using those hashtags allowed users to send their messages not only to their followers but to everyone who is tuned into that conversation and therefore reach a wider part of the public. Such a conversation is shown in the figure below.

²⁷⁵ The Saur Group. <https://www.facebook.com/pages/Saur/75804147857>

Figure 81: Twits concerning Xynthia storm by using the #xynthia hashtag.

Twitter was mainly used for discussing the effects of the storm but to also inform the population of the storm’s impact and any relevant news that would be of interest to them. A tweet by the Directorate of Legal and Administrative Information is shown below.²⁷⁶ The link on the tweet forwards the user to a webpage where he can read about compensation claims, map areas which are considered uninhabitable after the storm and about a public debate on 1393 houses in the Charente-Maritime and Vendée being subjected to demolition and their owners compensated by an average amount of 250,000 euros.

Figure 82²⁷⁷: Tweet from Directorate of Legal and Administrative Information.

²⁷⁶ Directorate of Legal and Administrative Information, <http://www.dila.premier-ministre.gouv.fr/>

²⁷⁷ <https://twitter.com/viepubliquefr/status/12276172990>

Flickr is a very rich repository of photographs for Xynthia but, just like the other social media cases, most of them were contributed after the event. Users uploaded photos on their own profiles but groups were also created where each user could contribute with his own set of photos (the two figures below illustrate this point). Discussions also took place in those groups where people discussed the catastrophe, paid tribute to the deceased and proposed ways of avoiding similar situations in the future.

Figure 83: Flickr images regarding Xynthia storm.

Figure 84: Flickr group containing photos of Xynthia storm.

Finally, in some rare cases, YouTube was also used. After the passage of the storm Xynthia the Saur group was supportive of communities and people in the most affected departments to restore drinking water to all households and provide human support, equipment and logistics

communities. Their activities were presented in their YouTube channel with videos such as the one shown below.²⁷⁸

Figure 85: YouTube video by the Saur Group presenting information about the storm and activities performed by the organization.

9.3 LESSONS LEARNED

According to partners' research and to the best of our knowledge, the social media use before, during and after the occurrence of the Xynthia storm by authorities was minimal. This could be partly explained by the fact that authorities only predicted the storm a few hours before it hit the French coast, but also because the storm itself only lasted a short amount of time.

Our research also showed that local authorities did not have social media accounts at the time and were therefore unable to provide help after the storm by informing the local populations of ways to face the flooding that had occurred.

It would undoubtedly be of great value to the public if authorities were more involved in the use of social media as it would provide an alternative method of providing information and aid to the affected population. For example, the Facebook page that was mentioned earlier in the chapter and was created with the purpose of offering support to the victims of Xynthia storm, illustrates the public's need to stay informed of ongoing support actions and help in any way possible. The creation of several other similar webpages in a variety of social media

²⁷⁸ Saur Group, <http://www.youtube.com/user/GroupeSaur>

by state and local authorities would have offered a number of support channels and therefore possibly reached a wider audience.

9.4 CONCLUSION

The Xynthia storm, compared to the other case studies of this deliverable, provided different results as to the main use of social media. Due to the nature of the disaster, with the authorities able to predict the storm only a few hours before it actually hit the coast of France, and the actual duration of the event, there was no time for social media to be used to either warn or provide advice as to how civilians could protect themselves. According to our knowledge, the authorities did not use social media in the aftermath of the disaster either, leaving several unanswered questions as to why that was the case.

Nevertheless, in this case study, social media were actively used by the public to campaign for support of the victims and exchange information and thoughts on the crisis. Facebook pages and groups were created and Twitter conversations also took place, by using the corresponding hashtags, as means to perform the aforementioned actions.

10 CONCLUSION

The purpose of Task 2.2 “Case studies on the use of new media in crisis situations” was for COSMIC to examine a series of European and international case studies in order to explore the ways in which new communication technologies and social media are being used in crisis situations today. Partners conducted an examination of eight different case studies, during which they described the nature of the case study, provided an understanding of how new and more conventional technologies as well as social media were used and discussed the lessons learned from the use (or lack of) of those technologies.

Specific case studies examined in this report are identified in the table below.

Table 3: Case studies included in this report

2013 Boston Marathon Bombing
2013 U.K. Heatwave
2012 Sandy Superstorm
2010 Haiti Earthquake
2013 Gezi Protests
2012 Colorado Wildfires
2012 U.K. Floods
2010 Xynthia Storm

Whilst each of the case studies supplied important lessons learned regarding the use of new communication technologies and social media, it is necessary to consider the findings across the different crises that were examined in Chapters 2 to 9 in order to determine some central elements relating to lessons learned from these case studies.

Conventional Communication Technologies

In the majority of cases, conventional communication technologies were used by the public and authorities to tackle some of the challenges that the crises posed. It is important to know that conventional technologies proved to still be involved in our everyday lives especially during crises. The overall conclusion of the examined case studies showed that it is still early days to consider relying on either conventional or new communication technologies and social media as being the only communication channel and crisis management tool available during a disaster.

In the U.K. heatwave case study, the Met Office transmitted warnings via email and the web to various organisations, including Public Health England, who would then use e-mail, the Internet, SMS messaging systems, television and radio broadcasts to disseminate warnings and health-related information to agencies and members of the public.

During the U.K. floods a floodline was opened for the public to be able to find out whether they were at risk of flooding. Eligible residents were also able to sign up to Floodline Warnings Direct, a free service that sends direct messages, by telephone, mobile, email, SMS text message or fax, when flooding is expected.

Certainly, new technologies provide an improvement and an alternative to previous technologies. This was illustrated in the Boston bombings where officials stated that landlines and cell phones would have been unreliable as both telephone systems were rendered largely inoperable due to the overloaded demand. In Haiti on the other hand, the use of conventional technologies for communicating after the earthquake was impossible, at least during the first few hours after the earthquake. As soon as the local infrastructure was repaired, information was broadcasted to survivors on how best to use their mobile phones to respond to the situation.

In the case of the Turkish protests in Gezi Park, little information was broadcast through traditional channels because they were considered as being biased against the protests. The Internet and social media were considered to be the major, if not the only, outlet through which the population could be informed about the protests and voice their opinions.

New Communication Technologies

As was previously mentioned, new communication technologies do offer an advantage over traditional methods and can not only help response agencies provide their services more efficiently and effectively to the public but can also possibly reach a larger part of the population.

New communication technologies were used quite extensively in the Boston bombings case study. Authorities responded to the bombings, by the use of interoperable radio hardware, an Emergency Patient Tracking software tool and the Wireless Emergency Alert system (WEA). Each of these systems offered improvements on previous information and communication tools that authorities had at their disposal.

On the other hand, during the U.K. heatwave of 2013 more established means of communication were used by the authorities to spread messages about the heatwave alert and the associated health risks. Partners found little information available about whether agencies used other newer forms of communication during the crisis. The same applies to the U.K. floods case study where authorities and other stakeholders mainly used the internet to broadcast warnings and alert the public of flooding danger around their area. There were also no evidence of the use of new communication technologies in the Xynthia case study.

In the Haiti earthquake case study however, new technologies were used in various ways. Haitians could use SMS to report missing persons, shelter problems and food issues, while the service also sent SMS texts with important information to registered users. Skype was also used by international mainstream media organisations to interview survivors.

During the Gezi Park protests new technologies were mostly used by the public as communication means. Such examples were SMS applications such as Whatsapp to form

information networks and Livestream and Ustream streaming applications used by citizen journalists to provide real-time coverage the protests.

New communication technologies played a significant role in the response to Hurricane Sandy, ranging from modern two-way radio deployments, through to mobile telephony technology, to novel web applications. WEA was also utilized by FEMA, as was the case with the Boston marathon bombings, to alert citizens of the incoming storm.

New technologies did not always produce positive results as was the case in the Colorado wildfires case study where one of the Emergency Notification Systems (ENS) used by the Jefferson County Emergency Communications Authority (JCECA) failed to work properly during the fire. This resulted in evacuation notifications either sent to the wrong addresses or not sent to the population that should have evacuated the area in danger.

Social Media

In all of the examined case studies, social media were used by a variety of stakeholders, ranging from state and local authorities, to response organizations and members of the public. New media applications have different functions, which should be respected when stakeholders try to determine what application to use for different purposes. COSMIC D2.1 *Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications* outlines six functions of social media in crisis situations:

1. One-way communication (notify/alert)

In most cases, with the exceptions of the Xynthia storm, the Haiti earthquake and the Gezi protests case studies, social media were used as a one-way communication channel between various stakeholders and the public. Twitter, Facebook, Google+ and Reddit were all utilised to alert the public of the imminent crisis and to advise them on how to prepare for it as well as recover after it was over.

In the aftermath of the Boston bombings, the authorities used social media to publicise suspect photos, share information about the bombing and announce the arrest of a suspect. Elsewhere, in preparation of hurricane Sandy, many organisations and individual responders used Twitter and Facebook to contact citizens in the affected region, informing them about the threat and providing information about measures that citizens should take before the storm arrives.

The Met Office used its Twitter, Facebook, Google+ and YouTube accounts to alert the population of the occurrence of the 2013 heatwave that hit the U.K. Similar action was taken by the Environmental Office during the U.K. floods of 2012, when it would regularly update

its social media accounts to better inform the affected population of flood warnings and to advise them of actions they could perform to mitigate the impact.

In other cases, such as the Colorado wildfires, social media were used not only by authorities but also by several businesses during the fires to inform their clients of current conditions concerning themselves and the situation in general.

2. Two-way communication (converse/provide feedback)

In all case studies, with the exception of Xynthia, where local authorities either did not have social accounts or did not use them, and the Gezi protests, where authorities did not use social media, stakeholders tried to not only inform but also to solicit information from the public regarding the crisis at hand.

For example, after the Boston bombings, the authorities requested that members of the public, who were present at the event, share images or video footage that they recorded. Later on, the FBI released the images of two suspects and solicited public help in naming them. During the U.K. heatwave UK Power Networks broadcasted information about power outages, and solicited information about power outages and vulnerable individuals from members of the public. During hurricane Sandy the American Red Cross learned about areas with power outages and flooded roads by receiving information from the public after they had broadcasted their own alerts.

The information being shared over social media after the Haiti earthquake often included urgent messages such as reports of injuries or of trapped people, as well as expressing important needs for instance regarding food and shelter in response to authorities' use of social media.

During the Colorado wildfires users could converse with local authorities mainly via their official Facebook and Twitter accounts. Similarly, during the U.K. floods, authorities and other organisations used their social media accounts to converse with the affected population.

3. Request/offer assistance

Social media were also used in some cases either by authorities and organisations to offer assistance or by members of the public to request assistance. Many organisations, such as the American Red Cross and the New York Fire Department, monitored social networks during hurricane Sandy and were able to respond according to the information they were receiving from individuals. During the Gezi protests, 13% of the survey's respondents indicated that by learning about the events via social media as to where police were organised, and where people were being injured, they could mobilise and provide assistance to the protestors. Haitians also used social media, mainly Twitter to communicate with each other and ask for assistance.

4. Relay (share a piece of information with others)

In all of the examined case studies social media were used by the public to relay information posted online by the different stakeholders participating in the crisis management process. In some case studies more than others the public was more aware of the need to re-share potentially vital information among their own friends and followers.

For example, a tweet from the Boston marathon organisers was retweeted 3,671 times, while in the U.K. heatwave case study a Facebook post by the Met Office was re-shared 80 times. During Gezi protests, people who use Twitter for getting and sharing information constituted the largest segment with 47% of the survey's respondents.

20 million Tweets were sent out regarding hurricane Sandy but we do not know the percentage of those which were actual retweets of an original tweet. Even though social media, such as Facebook and Twitter, were also used after the Haiti earthquake, partners' research did not produce exact figures as to the percentage of information relayed among the posts and tweets.

The Colorado wildfires case study showed that people need to be reminded to re-share information. Tweets and posts by authorities were rarely shared while posts by a local news agency were re-shared hundreds of times. This was because in their original post the agency urged people to share the information they provided.

During the U.K. floods and the Xynthia storm partners did identify the use of social media with the purpose of relaying information but to a far lesser extent compared to other case studies. There were only few times where content by authorities was actually re-shared.

5. Campaign (awareness raising/fund raising)

In several cases social media were used to for campaign purposes. In Haiti for example, organisations such as the American Red Cross turned to social media to raise donations. In Gezi protests, more than 20% of the examined survey respondents' Tweets were oriented towards raising public awareness about police misconduct. Finally, after the Xynthia storm, several Facebook pages were created, campaigning for support to the victims of the storm as well as raising awareness about the government's plans of demolishing houses in "black areas".

6. Organise (co-ordinate response/enable individuals to organise themselves)

Crowdsourcing after the Haiti earthquake helped organise first responders on the ground, to deal with needs according to relevance and urgency. During the Gezi protests social media were also used by 13% of the survey's respondents for coordination and organisation

purposes. Finally, Facebook pages were created during the U.K floods of 2012 to try to organize the public and recruit volunteers.

Lessons Learned

We have seen that social media can play a key role before, during and after a disaster has occurred. The lessons learned by examining the case studies in this chapter are summarised below:

- Telecommunications infrastructures and services may suffer outages during a disaster – some affected citizens may have an operational land-line but no data network connectivity, while for others the reverse may be true thanks to cable or mobile data connections. Therefore, simultaneous use of traditional and new technologies is required for authorities and other stakeholders to be able to reach as much part of the affected population as possible.
- It is highly unlikely that major organisations' Facebook and Twitter pages will be offline during a crisis. Social media can act as counterbalance when conventional warning systems fail to operate, like the case was with the Emergency Notification System (ENS) used by the Jefferson County Emergency Communications Authority. Therefore, authorities should not neglect to monitor and update their social media pages regularly.
- Social media users should not just visit online pages just to inform themselves about the current situation but instead be involved as much as possible in the dissemination of the information by re-sharing and retweeting potentially valuable information to people in need.
- Organisations should not pay attention to low interest in their social media accounts during the absence of crises. Establishing a social media strategy before a crisis occurs is important.
- Social media can be used to correct misinformation being circulated by members of the public and to share breaking news with the mass media.
- Different types of messages are relevant to different audiences. Organisations should consider the kinds of information that is most desired by an online audience, at different points in time, and for different sectors of the public.
- Officials and major crisis responders should agree upon unique, but intuitive hashtags prior to major events in order to facilitate information sharing and avoid significant

amount of extraneous information, including advertisements, personal commentary and international information.

- There are also significant risks (mentioned in the next section) involved in the use of social media. Social media may be used for the dissemination of deceitful, fraudulent, incorrect or misleading information.
- Social media usage can be aggregated to discover information not present in individual messages. Aggregates provide information ranging from *which* topics are trending, to tracking or recognising the movements or patterns of movement of large numbers of individuals.
- Social media are a powerful tool for raising awareness and donations to aid crisis-stricken populations.
- With more and more people actively being involved in social media, authorities do not have the luxury of not participating in this new kind of communication with the public. The lack of social media accounts by authorities and organisations prohibits them from providing the best possible support to the affected population.

Risks

Even though the use of new communication technologies and social media before, during and after a crisis was in the majority of cases a success, there are some risks and shortcomings to consider.

This is evident in case studies such as the Boston bombings, the Sandy storm and the Haiti earthquake. Specifically, in the aftermath of the Boston bombing, the wrongful identification of suspects and the sharing of confidential police information could have endangered both citizens, who might have been falsely portrayed as those responsible for the attack by members of the public, as well as officers.

Different kinds of risks were identified in the other two case studies, mainly using social media to spread false rumours and falsehoods, which may be accidental or of malicious intent, as well as to post bogus donations on behalf of official support organisations. Furthermore, the utilisation of social media, rather than conventional channels such as calling the emergency phone line 911 to report emergency information, can also be considered as potential misuse. Emergency response services will most likely focus on traditional channels, at least at the early stages of the crisis, before turning their attention to requests for help coming from social media.

Finally, there lies a risk in mainstream media misusing social media in their effort to provide quick news coverage to an event. Mainstream media are under great pressure to deliver timely reports. However, with social media breaking news within minutes of events occurring, the ability of mainstream media to ascertain the validity of content arriving from social media is small (while their own reporters will not be able to always be on-the-spot when, where and as major events occur). Thus, they are under pressure to use social media as sources, as fast as possible, while at the same time being aware that verifying the incoming information is difficult. There is a real risk of main-stream media erring on the side of speed rather than that of correctness and accuracy.

ACRONYMS

B	
BBC	British Broadcasting Corporation
C	
CCTV	Closed Circuit Television
E	
EIS project	Emergency Information Service
ENS	Emergency Notification System
F	
FBI	Federal Bureau of Investigation
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Association
FCC	Federal Communications Commission
FDNY	New York Fire Department
H	
HRT	Hellenic Rescue Team
I	
IPAWS	Integrated Public Alert and Warning System
InSTEDD	Innovative Support To Emergencies, Diseases and Disasters
ISP	Internet Service Provider
ICTs	Information and Communication Technologies
J	
JCECA	Jefferson County Emergency Communications Authority
M	
Met Office	UK Meteorological Office
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectrometer
MPS	Metropolitan Police Service
N	
NHS	National Health Service
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NGO	Non-Government Organisation
NWS	National Weather Service
S	
SAR	Search and rescue
SCHAPI	Service Central d’Hydrométéorologie et d’Appui à la Prévision des Inondations”
SHOM	Naval Hydro - graphical and Oceanographic Department
U	
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
W	
WEA	Wireless Emergency Alerts